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International Migration, Adult Education, and Open Education: A global analysis

International Migration,
Adult Education, and
Open Education:
A global analysis

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Research Coordination and Supervision

Rodrigo Matos-de-Souza - University of Brasília (UnB)

Redaction

Milan Puh - University of Bahia (UFBA)

Rodrigo Matos-de-Souza - University of Brasília (UnB)

Revision

Rodrigo Matos-de-Souza - University of Brasília (UnB)

Tel Amiel - University of Brasília (UnB)

Graphic Design

Isabela Campos Menezes - UNESCO Chair in Open Education and Technologies for the Common Good (UnB)

Coordinator of the UNESCO Chair in Open Education and Technologies for the Common Good (UnB)

Tel Amiel – University of Brasília (UnB)

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| SUMMARY

This study aimed to produce State-of-the-art bibliographical research on migration and its intersection with Adult Education and Open and Distance Education. It looks at international migration, especially refugee migration, in the educational policies of the world's main trading blocs and the main global economies compared with Brazilian policies at the national and subnational level in theoretical and methodological legal terms, highlighting the conceptual changes and the most recent problematizations.

The main concepts used during the research are presented to discuss the methodological aspects, context, and justification of the blocs and countries chosen for this report. We close with the main conclusions and considerations on the subject. The text presents an extensive descriptive bibliography, a rich basis for future studies on this subject.

The text is organized into two strands of analysis, presented in sequence. First, an analysis of the policies of Europe and the Americas, and second, Africa, Asia, and Oceania are presented below.

| INTRODUCTION

This report presents the results of a data survey on Migration as it intersects with Adult Education and Open and Distance Education. The first part of the survey focused on the American and European continents and, later on, the Asian, African, and Oceanic continents. A better understanding of the types of education mentioned and migration/displacement is important because countless adult foreigners are entering Brazilian territory, arriving in places where face-to-face study in basic or higher education institutions is often impossible. A better understanding of the place and potential, for example, of Open Educational Resources (OERs) for the inclusion of this population is essential for drawing up more democratic and comprehensive policies.

Therefore, special interest will be in how Adult Education and Open and Distance Education are covered in compositions aimed at different people affected by displacement/migration. To do this, it will be necessary to define categories that will make it possible to integrate these educational aspects into a comprehensive study. Therefore, it could provide the means for future implementation of research activities, training, promotion, and dissemination of public policies in Brazil, especially in the context of UNESCO's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), such as quality education, reduction of inequalities, peace, justice, and efficient institutions, and partnerships and means of implementation.

The focus is mainly on these specific objectives since the proposal aims to help raise the quality of education for the entire population living in Brazilian territory, giving more visibility to and encouraging the inclusion of migrant groups and broadening the processes of democratization of education as a whole and, with this, acting to make educational institutions more efficient, while at the same time suggesting future partnerships in networks of different agents and thinking about how to implement specific policies.

To meet the focus, it is important to initially carry out a brief conceptualization of the terms Migration, Displacement, Refuge, Open Education, Distance Education, and Adult Education, as defined by the bodies we consulted in the survey of best practices and policies. In the context of the second part of this report, we consider it important to highlight more specific terms that have recurrently appeared in the surveys, namely, women migrants, the kafala system, and climate migrants.

| Migration

Migration is a flow of people who, for different reasons such as fleeing armed

conflicts or persecution or because they are looking for a better life, move to another country and stay there, meeting minimum criteria set by national states in terms of time, such as length of residence, and meeting distance criteria, which exclude internal displacement, travel for various interests and tourism. Although there is no formal legal definition of an international migrant, there is consensus in the field that an international migrant is someone who changes their country of habitual residence on a permanent basis, regardless of whether or not:

- I. their legal status;
- II. reason for migration (voluntary or involuntary);
- III. causes that provoked the movement; and,
- IV. length of stay in a place.

The number of international migrants worldwide — people living in a country other than their country of birth — reached almost 283 million in 2023, of which 110 million are refugees (Migration Data Portal, 2023). In order to understand the statistics and characteristics of how the migration process takes place, it is important to observe its multiple identity and social intersectionalities such as gender, race, class, sexual orientation, ethnicity, religion, and many others that help to understand the issue beyond individual/group objectives or conjunctural social, political, environmental and/or economic reasons (Campos, 2017; Matos-de-Souza et al., 2020; IOM, 2022).

| Refuge

Refuge is a vital survival mechanism in times of social or political crisis. The provision of refuge includes the whole range of services necessary to constitute the refugee's citizenship, including housing, health, education, and food. The diversity of practices in the reception of refugees is fundamental to restoring the personal security, self-sufficiency, and dignity of populations who suffer any kind of threat from the government of their country of origin. As defined by the 1951 Geneva Convention, refuge can be applied to people who, because of a well-founded fear of persecution for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion, find themselves outside the country of their nationality or origin, making them unable or, because of this fear, unwilling to return to it (UNHCR, 1951). This concept was later broadened in the 1984 Cartagena Declaration (UNHCR, 1984), which explicitly extended its scope to situations of individual persecution and not just group persecution, as in the case of political asylum seekers, incorporating aspects of human rights that are denied in this case, causing the person to move from their original residence. As a result, the refugee becomes a citizen of the country where he finds asylum, receiving the necessary assistance to rebuild his life and that of his family from international and multilateral institutions and organizations, such as the UN and UNESCO, and the government itself.

| Displacements

Displacement can be defined as the movement of groups and/or communities seeking to escape armed conflicts, environmental emergencies, or any other event that threatens their physical well-being. It can occur both inside and outside national border lines. In other cases, we can highlight the displacement of populations from countries belonging to the same economic bloc and/or continent of birth, such as local populations in Latin America who move between countries in search of jobs and better living conditions. Unlike refugee status, the term displacement is used to delimit the population's movement beyond the social agent's political status before the international community and their potential authorization to remain in another country (Feldman-Bianco, 2017).

| Open Education

Open Education — OE is a proposal that aims to provide broad and open access to education, often with projects aimed at higher education as the main focus. The main premise is the removal of barriers preventing the free circulation of knowledge in society and the construction of digital platforms that make such access possible for students from the widest range of social backgrounds. The materials used in open education are made available on platforms that allow free access, reuse, repurposing, adaptation, and redistribution by others. The OE model can be used for Adult Education, facilitating access and enabling Education, i.e. Lifelong Learning, and having a direct dialog with the Distance Education format. This is because it aims to overcome the obstacles faced by migrant populations, who are often not in a position to study in person or continuously but who need additional training or retraining to guarantee their own livelihoods and ensure their fulfillment and transformation as individuals and members of their communities and societies. This proposal aims to broaden the connection between formal and non-formal education, taking cognizance of the contemporary condition of education, in which school institutions do not have a monopoly on education, having their practice in more traditional spaces and in others that are more avant-garde (European Union, 2022).

| Distance education — DE

Distance education describes a set of teaching and learning strategies (or educational methods) that can overcome the spatial and temporal separation between educators and learners. This teaching-learning modality can be carried out in multiple formats, emphasizing its temporal condition. It can be subdivided in real-time between asynchronous and synchronous or accessing previously

executed and recorded classes. It often constitutes hybrid modes of study between face-to-face and remote. Given its versatility, distance learning not only presents itself as a pedagogical alternative to educational institutions but can also be used in contexts where access to education is more difficult. It is a relatively important tool for formulating a policy of democratic access to education (Maclean & Wilson, 2009).

| Adult education — AE

Adult education is a multidisciplinary process aimed at improving professional qualifications and achieving civic, social, and cultural attitudes and skills for fulfilling responsibilities and progressing in all spheres of life. Adult education has three central areas of learning: literacy and basic skills; continuing education and professional development (professional skills); and liberal, popular, and community education (active citizenship skills). Similar to Distance Education and Open Education, Adult Education recognizes the value and relevance of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) as having great potential to improve adults' access to a variety of learning opportunities, resulting in greater equity, inclusion, and transformation, as advocated by Learning and Knowledge Technologies (LKT) and Technologies for Empowerment and Participation (TEP). Adult learners can access learning opportunities anytime and anywhere via mobile devices, electronic networks, social media, and online courses (UNESCO, 2019).

| Migrant women

These are women who have moved (or are in the process/attempt of moving) to one country from another, who suffer from specific migration conditions linked to their gender in the territories in question. In addition, the move (or attempt to move) may not always be voluntary. There are cases in which women are taken to another country against their will or under pressure, foreseeing their future exploitation. In other contexts, compulsory departure from a territory may result from economic, natural, or environmental disasters (European Union, 2023).

| Climate migrant

Another important type is the climate-driven migrant, due to changes that have disastrous effects on the economy and territories affected. However, these people are not legally considered refugees since this term has a specific meaning centered on a "well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion" (UNHCR, 1951). The most socially and economically vulnerable groups

tend to be the hardest hit as well as the fact that the exact number of this type of migrant is unknown, given the lack of instruments to define the metrics for identifying them. It should also be said that specific groups, such as women and ethnic minorities, will be hit hardest by the effects of climate change. According to the UN (UN, 2021), they account for 80% of all climate migrants, but this does not apply to all Asian countries since, in the case of China, this percentage is 40%.

| Migrant in the Kafala system

Another specific type of migrant we observed in the survey is the one who comes from the Kafala system, which is still common in Jordan, Lebanon, and all the Gulf countries except Iraq. It is defined by a legal framework that has for decades defined the relationship between migrant workers and their employers. In this framework, the state grants sponsorship permits to local individuals or companies to employ foreign workers. The sponsor/employer covers travel expenses and provides housing, often in dormitory-type accommodation or, in the case of domestic workers, in the sponsor/employer's home. In most situations, workers need their sponsor's permission to change jobs, terminate employment, and enter or leave the host country. Leaving the workplace without permission often results in the termination of the worker's legal status and, potentially, imprisonment or deportation, making their migrant status very vulnerable and making it difficult for them to get an adequate education (CFR, 2023), which by Western standards of analysis is similar to being reduced to a condition analogous to slavery.

■ METHODOLOGY

In order for this report to be produced, a methodological proposal for the elements/steps of the survey was initially defined. This proposal involved an approach to educational practices and policies at the international, national, and subnational/regional levels, proposing conceptual and critical reflections on how to search for and systematize what is produced in different territories and at different times. Subsequently, a systematization and bibliometric and scientometric analysis were carried out, followed by a stage of analysis of the generated data based on the policy cycle approach and, finally, producing a text with the results focused on the context of the two continental blocs. The detailed methodological processes are available in [Annex I](#).

■ CONTEXT AND JUSTIFICATIONS

After defining the methodology for searching, organizing, and analyzing best practices and policies focused on the theme of Migration and Human Displacement in its intersection with three types of education: Adult, Open, and Distance, it was decided to define the context (space-territory) to search for these practices and policies of the theme in question, opting for the choice of trading blocs, since their directions and compositions end up generating a cascade effect that affects the individual member countries and also interferes with the way other places in the world organize themselves.

In the first part, we examined a few countries: Mexico, the United States, and Canada. These stand out for their specificities in quantitative terms (number of migrants and composition aimed at them) and qualitative terms (quality of composition to meet their different needs), given that their trading blocs, NAFTA/USMCA, did not have many compositions to draw on in this report.

In the second, we paid closer attention to a few countries: China, India, Taiwan, Estonia, Turkey, Australia and Lebanon, the first two of which stand out for their political and economic importance and population size, while the only country in Oceania stands out in both quantitative terms (number of migrants and composition aimed at them) and qualitative terms (quality of composition to meet their different needs), since its trading blocs (RCEP/ASEAN) didn't have as many compositions that could be used in this report. The last three countries, although small in political and economic importance and size, represent places of transition between the blocs and regions, serving as beacons for understanding the transitions between the continents and territories of these great spaces. In Brazil, an individual survey was carried out to compare and elucidate the specificities of national production.

■ REFERENCES

Alto Comissariado das Nações Unidas para os Refugiados – ACNUR (1951). Convenção relativa ao estatuto dos refugiados. https://www.acnur.org/fileadmin/Documentos/portugues/BDL/Convencao_relativa_ao_Estatuto_dos_Refugiados.pdf

Alto Comissariado das Nações Unidas para os Refugiados -ACNUR (1984). Declaração de Cartagena. https://www.acnur.org/fileadmin/Documentos/portugues/BD_Legal/Instrumentos_Internacionais/Declaracao_de_Cartagena.pdf

Campos, M. B (2017). Migração In L. Cavalcanti, L, T. Botega, T. Tonhati, T & D. Araújo (Orgs.). Dicionário Crítico de Migrações Internacionais. Brasília: Editora UnB.

Council on Foreign Relations – CFR (2023). What Is the Kafala System? <https://www.cfr.org/background/what-kafala-system>.

European Union. (2022, 2 de fevereiro). What is open education? In: EU Science Hub. https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/what-open-education_en

European Union (2023). Migrant women. Instituto Europeu para Igualdade de Género. <https://eige.europa.eu/thesaurus/terms/1292>.

Feldman-Bianco, B. (2017). Deslocamento. L. Cavalcanti, L, T. Botega, T. Tonhati, T & D. Araújo (Orgs.). Dicionário Crítico de Migrações Internacionais. Brasília: Editora UnB.

International Organization for Migration - IOM, 2022. People on the Move in a Changing Climate – Linking Policy, Evidence and Action. IOM, Geneva. <https://publications.iom.int/books/people-move-changing-climate-linking-policy-evidence-and-action>

Maclean, R., Wilson, D. (Eds.) (2009). International Handbook of Education for the Changing World of Work: Volume 1. Dordrecht, Netherlands: Springer Science.

Matos-de-Souza, R., Lazarini, T., González-Monteagudo, J., & Barroso-Tristán, J. M. (2021). Migration and education: A study on the invisibilization of the migrant in Brazilian and Federal District educational policies. Education Policy Analysis Archives, 29 (January - July), 24. <https://doi.org/10.14507/epaa.29.5540>

Migration Data Portal (2023). International data. https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs_&t=2020

Organização das Nações Unidas – ONU (2021). COP26: 80% dos deslocados por desastres e mudanças climáticas são mulheres. <https://brasil.un.org/pt-br/157806-cop26-80-dos-deslocados-por-desastres-e-mudancas-climaticas-sao-mulheres>.

UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning. (2019). 4th global report on adult learning and education: leave no one behind: participation, equity and inclusion. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000372274>

Trading blocs:
AMERICAS AND EUROPE

This summarizes all the blocs consulted in the report, considering their political and economic weight globally.

| NAFTA/USMCA

The North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) is an agreement between Canada, Mexico, and the United States that allows free trade with reduced costs for exchanging goods between the three countries. NAFTA entered into force on January 1, 1994. In 2017, trade between the bloc's countries reached 1.2 trillion dollars (AS/COA, 2017). The United States-Mexico-Canada Agreement (USMCA) is the agreement that replaces the North American Free Trade Agreement. The document was signed by the Canadian prime minister and the United States and Mexico presidents on November 30, 2018, during the 2018 G20 Summit in Buenos Aires, Argentina. According to the World Economics data repository (2012-2022), the USMCA is the second largest economic bloc in the world, behind the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP). These countries account for 17% of global GDP and 11% of global GDP growth over the last ten years (2011-2021). Given this scenario, the bloc is highly relevant. It has an international projection, and it is interesting to analyze its possible legislation on educational development and the reception of migrants and refugees.

| MERCOSUR

The Southern Common Market (MERCOSUR) is a regional integration process initially established by Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, Uruguay, and later Venezuela and Bolivia. It has an estimated GDP of US\$2.68 trillion. According to the official MERCOSUR¹ website, the countries included in the agreement cover 14,869,775 km² and have a population of 295,007,000, making it the fifth largest economy globally. US\$824,000,000 has been invested in infrastructure. According to the Migration Data Portal organization, South America has particular migratory patterns, with significant internal and external migration and a strong wave of emigration. According to the portal, the region has more than 17 million emigrants and 10 million immigrants. In this sense, given the migrant patterns present in the bloc, we can study it from different migratory perspectives, making it extremely relevant not only because of its regional value for Brazil.

¹ Retrieved from: <https://www.mercosur.int/pt-br/>. Accessed on 11/10/2022.

| ANDEAN COMMUNITY

The Andean Community is a South American economic bloc comprising Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, and Peru. According to its official website², the Andean community has 111 million inhabitants in an area of 4.7 million square kilometers, with a nominal gross domestic product of 280 billion dollars. Like the rest of South America, the Andean Community has diverse migratory patterns of emigration and immigration. According to its official website, the Andean Community also has a Migratory Statute that regulates the community's right of movement between the member countries and establishes temporary and permanent residence for Andean citizens in those countries. Thus, similar to MERCOSUR, it is a regional integration agreement, not just an economic one, making the migratory aspect generated by this type of agreement very relevant for analysis.

| EUROPEAN UNION

The European Union (EU) is a supranational political and economic union of 27 member states in Europe. According to Marek Hlavac (2010), the union has a total area of 4,233,255.3 km² and an estimated total population of around 447 million. It has often been described as a sui generis political entity (without precedent or comparison) that combines the characteristics of a federation and a confederation. Because of its unique political nature, the EU has a strong international profile and a wide range of treaties, agreements, and resolutions, among others, on the most diverse socio-economic topics, especially migration and education. According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the EU accounted for 5.8% of the world's population in 2020 and generated a nominal gross domestic product (GDP) of around US\$17.1 trillion in 2021, constituting approximately 18% of global nominal GDP. In addition, according to the United Nations Development Program, all EU states have a very high Human Development Index (HDI). Because of these economic and legislative peculiarities, approximately 47.3 million people living in the EU have been born outside their country of residence since 2010, corresponding to 9.4% of the total EU population. In this sense, studying migration and political asylum legislation and particularities in the bloc is very relevant.

² Retrieved from: <https://www.comunidadandina.org/>. Accessed on 11/17/2022.

■ AMERICAS

Considering the specificities of Brazil and the three countries that are part of NAFTA/USMCA—Canada, the USA, and Mexico—we decided to present these four countries individually since the NAFTA/USMCA bloc did not present satisfactory results at this level, requiring a closer look at each of the countries.

| USA

According to the Migration Policy Institute (2022), 44.9 million immigrants of various origins live in the United States, making the country extremely significant in terms of numbers regarding the different migratory waves present in the Americas and extremely relevant for analysis.

| Canada

According to the Migration Policy Institute (2022), foreign-born permanent residents represent more than 20% of Canada's population, and newly arrived immigrants now account for more than 50% of the annual population growth. This is another extremely significant figure in the context of the Americas, in this case as a proportion of the population, making it relevant to the analysis.

| Mexico

Also, according to the Migration Policy Institute (2022), 97% of Mexican migrants living abroad are in the USA, marking a clear phenomenon of internal migration between NAFTA/USMCA member countries. It is interesting to analyze this phenomenon comparatively between the member countries and their legislation and initiatives concerning migration.

| Brazil

According to the International Migration Observatory's annual report for 2020, between 2011 and 2019, 1,085,673 immigrants were registered in Brazil, and 660,349 long-term immigrants were registered in Brazil between 2010 and 2019. Nationals of Venezuela (142,250), Paraguay (97,316), Bolivia (57,765), and Haiti (54,182) are among the largest number of long-term migrant residents in the country, accounting for 53% of the records. Brazil, a member state of Mercosur and the base country for this survey has a significant immigrant and refugee population, making it relevant to study the educational policies for welcoming these populations.

■ MAIN CONCLUSIONS AND CONSIDERATIONS

This part of the report will present some conclusions and considerations that emerged during the database's survey, organization, and evaluation. The survey revealed a lack of policies and practices linking the three types of education — open, Distance, and Adult Education — to the immigrant/refugee population. This indicates the incipience of interdisciplinary studies, especially those in the field of Open Education.

Open Education itself has appeared more recently in the surveys, with several sites gathering materials and resolutions that help regulate and organize it. However, the results show that this is an isolated composition, with no association with the idea of immigrants and refugees, and that the whole area lacks this integration. The trend identified is to link distance education with education for immigrants and refugees, and in this case, more elements are also aimed specifically at adult audiences.

Secondly, the difficulty was revealed when searching for compositions aimed at adult audiences since many documents, legislation, programs, and initiatives exist for school-age children and adolescents. Adult Education was detected almost entirely in general education documents, while the documents on Youth Education were produced separately. In practical terms, Adult Immigrant and Refugee Education usually receives legal and juridical attention on the American and European continents, with more emphasis on continuing education or lifelong learning.

The biggest producers of legislation, strategies, guidelines, evaluations, tools, and resources are the international organizations: the UN, IOM, and UNESCO, especially the latter. UNESCO has stood out with various policies, including: "Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies: Open Education for a Better World" and "Directrizes para recursos educacionais abertos (REA): no ensino superior," as well as with practices and compositions, such as regional observatory "Information System on Educational Trends in Latin America (SITEAL)" and websites with resources "Open Educational Resources (OER)," "International Council for Open and Distance Education (IODE)," "Open Education for a Better World," "Language and Literacy Programs for migrants and Refugees: challenges and Ways Forward Open Education for a Better World" and "Integrating Migration into Education Interventions: A Toolkit for International Cooperation and Development Actors," made in partnership with IOM and the

EU. Future work in the area would have to make more detailed analyses of the compositions we find on the sites, i.e., the electronic repositories they keep, to understand what kind of databases are set up there. In addition, we have pointed out the lack of integration between different types of education and the immigrant/refugee public.

As pointed out earlier, the trading blocs on the two continents deal with the issue in different ways. The main difference here is comparing NAFTA/USMCA to the other blocs because its production of legislation and agreements on immigration/refugees and education has been restricted to the economic issue. MERCOSUR and the Andean Community have education as one of the pillars of their internal organization. However, the topic of migration is defined more in terms of the movement of people. In the case of the EU, there is a strong relation between education and immigration, which is due to the phenomenon of migration/refugee that Europe has seen in recent years, as well as a willingness on the part of its political structures to produce not only materials but also regulations and programs that should help in the organization of curricula, defining action plans: "Action Plan for Digital Education 2021-2027", "Action Plan for Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027", a way of acting that is more propositional and allows projections for the future. In addition, in the EU, we find networks and centers that integrate different member countries and their institutions, for example: "Eurydice - European information network on education systems and policies," European Digital Education Hub" and "European Education Area," yet another practice that could be reflected positively in the future, finding a parallel in the Open Education initiative in Brazil or the Open and Distance University in Mexico. Finally, it is a space where electronic sites such as Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), Open Educational Resources (OER), and a site that articulates three types of resources: "Open Education: OER, OCW, and MOOCs " exist, which can serve as an example for repositories that integrate different kinds of tools and resources throughout Brazil and the world.

At this point we will also present the specific countries taken into account in our survey.

| Canada

Legislation is produced to a lesser degree than the production of practice/materials (or at least the material does not make it explicit which program/law it is part of, giving the impression that there was not much articulation between the sphere of textual production and practice), which also gives the impression that there is not much integration between policies and practices. There is a balance between immigrants learning French and English, but with a tendency to isolate the languages, offering one or the other, not both, which makes us wonder about the place that bilingualism and multilingualism have in the thinking and functioning of those who think about the subject.

| United States

There is a large production of legislation, while materials are less produced compared to Canada. The migratory issue is also noteworthy. Even when it is positively viewed in favor of immigrants/refugees, problematic elements are pointed out and organized to help the migrant public solve the bureaucratic order's most basic needs. Thus, materials are produced that solve problems, such as school enrollment, for example, and do not necessarily define what practices or policies can be defined to make education work better, taking advantage of the presence of immigrants, in this case.

| Mexico

In this country's case, its relation with the US is a major factor. When the same 26 terms were used in English, there were results related to the "problem" of Mexicans in the United States, while when the search was done in Spanish, the results were more focused on Mexico and from its perspective. This situation reinforces the importance of conducting research in addition to English to try to balance out the possible bias that linguistic use can cause. Another important factor in Mexico's case is the concern about the return and integration of its migrant population into Mexican society.

| Brazil

Greater coordination was possible between international organizations, especially the UNHCR and UNESCO, national public bodies, and higher education institutions and their initiatives. This means there is a greater articulation between what is proposed at the international level and its regional and local developments. This seems to be a favorable path for the expansion of this area, which is also in its infancy in Brazil but which has this specificity that could help in greater future articulation of the different types of education and the immigrant/refugee public. However, we have not yet found many policies or legislation dedicated to the issue at the state or federal level, with more examples at the municipal level (São Paulo city hall). Still, regarding the existence of sites and repositories, there is some accumulation of experience in compositions such as: "Escolha Livre" (Free Choice), "Mapa de Serviços Abertos" (Open Services Map) and "Observatório Educação Vigiada" (Watched Education Observatory), the latter of which takes a critical look at the use of so-called "free providers" of storage services: Google, Microsoft, etc., something that was not found on either continent.

Considering all that has been mentioned and discussed in this report, we can conclude that the area of Open Education in its relationship with Distance and Adult Education, thinking of the immigrant/refugee public, needs

I. more in-depth studies of specific compositions, both political and practical, and other more panoramic studies, making interconnections between the different types of Education;

II. surveys, as a state-of-the-art that would systematize and critically analyze the production carried out in different government spheres (municipalities, state and federal governments, basic and government spheres (municipalities, state and federal governments, basic and higher education institutions), non-governmental institutions and for-profit and non-profit companies/organizations;

III. unifying repositories of different resources and tools and repositories of institutional policies on (inter)national issues and;

IV. initiatives that result in events, networks, and programs/action plans that offer more direct guidelines and proposals on how to benefit the adult migrant and refugee population through Open and Distance Education.

Regarding the initiatives that articulate the main themes of this report, we can highlight, concerning the production of strategic documents, studies, and reports, the publications produced by the UN and IOM, namely the strategic document entitled "Refugee Education 2030: a strategy for refugee inclusion"; the case study "Inter-Agency Network for Education in Emergencies: A community of practice, a catalyst for change"; the document "Data Transformation Strategy 2020-2025 Supporting protection and solutions" and the report "Education and Migration: an assessment of the types and range of IOM's education and vocational training projects". Among the guides and manuals produced by different countries, those from Canada and Mexico stand out in particular: the manual "Découvrir le Canada: les droits et responsabilités liés à la citoyenneté" and the guide "¡Elige, aprende y supérate! guía educativa para mexicanos en el exterior y en retorno". Finally, the "Integrating Migration into Education Interventions: A Toolkit for International Cooperation and Development Actors, produced by the EU, UNESCO, and UNICEF, is an important initiative that can help develop programs and projects that integrate the themes of migration and open, distance, and adult education.

The significant dependence on multilateral, governmental, and state bodies also indicates that the private sector, third-sector organizations, and even universities are distant from the interdisciplinary debate articulating Open, Distance, and Adult Education. Finally, we believe that because they are immersed in the territory, especially in Latin America, where extension plays a fundamental role in offering services to the population, universities could be more involved in providing education to migrant populations, favoring open and distance education, precisely because of its economic nature and its greater capacity to certify and validate training courses before migration.

■ REFERENCES

Batalova, J. (2022). Top Statistics on Global Migration and Migrants. In: Migration Policy Institute. Disponible em:

<https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/top-statistics-global-migration-migrants#:~:text=The%20number%20of%20persons%20forcibly,the%20United%20Nations%20High%20Commissioner.>

Bolivia. International Organization for Migration. (2022). Making Migration Work for All. Disponible em: <https://www.iom.int/countries/bolivia>.

Bolter, J. (2022). Immigration Has Been a Defining, Often Contentious, Element Throughout U.S. History. In: Migration Policy Institute. Disponible em:

<https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/immigration-shaped-united-states-history>.

Challinor, A. E. (2011). Canada's Immigration Policy: a Focus on Human Capital. In: Migration Policy Institute. Disponible em: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/canadas-immigration-policy-focus-human-capital>.

Colombia. Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística. (2021). Visualizador de Datos Estadísticas de Migración. Disponible em:

<https://sitios.dane.gov.co/visor-migracion-nacional/index.html>.

Comunidad Andina. (2021). Aprueban Estatuto Migratorio Andino que establece Residencia Temporal y Permanente en países de la CAN. Disponible em:

<https://www.comunidadandina.org/notas-de-prensa/aprueban-estatuto-migratorio-andino-que-establece-residencia-temporal-y-permanente-en-paises-de-la-can/>

Destatis, Statistisches Bundesamt. (2022). Migration and Integration. Disponible em: https://www.destatis.de/EN/Themes/Society-Environment/Population/Migration-Integration/_node.html.

Hellenic Republic. (2021). Press Release: Estimated Population (2021) and Migration Flows (2020). Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT), Grecia.

Hlavac, M. (2010). Less Than a state, more than an international organization: The Sui generis nature of the European Union. MPRA Paper n. 27179.

Institut National D'études Démographiques (2020). How many immigrants are there in France? Disponible em:

https://www.ined.fr/en/everything_about_population/demographic-facts-sheets/faq/how-many-immigrants-france/.

Instituto Nacional de Estadística. (2021). Cifras de Población (CP) a 1 de enero de 2022 Estadística de Migraciones (EM) Año 2021 Datos provisionales. Espanha.

International Monetary Fund. World Economic and Financial Surveys. (2022). World: Economic Outlook Database. Disponível em: <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO/weo-database/2022/October/weo-report?a=1&c=998,&s=NGDPD,PPPGDP,PPPCC,&sy=2021&ey=2022&ssm=0&scsm=0&sc=0&ssd=1&ssc=0&sic=0&sort=country&ds=.&br=1>.

Itália. Istituto Nazionale Di Statistica. (2021). Indicatori Demografici: Anno 2020. Disponível em: <https://www.as-coa.org/articles/chart-nafta-numbers-2017>.

Mercosur. (2022). Website of The Southern Common Market. Disponível em: <https://www.mercosur.int/en>.

Migration Data Portal. (2021). Migration data in South America. Disponível em: https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs_&t=2020&m=2&sm49=5

Observatório das Migrações Internacionais. (2020). Resumo Executivo - Relatório Anual do Obmigra.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2012). Key indicators by country. Disponível em: <https://www.oecd.org/migration/integration-indicators-2012/keyindicatorsbycountry/name,218347,en.htm>.

OECD,iLibrary. (2020). International Migration Outlook. Disponível em: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/international-migration-outlook-2020_ec98f531-en.html

Stabel Belgium in figures. (2022). On 1 January 2022, the legal population in Belgium was 11,584,008 inhabitants. Disponível em: <https://statbel.fgov.be/en/news/1-january-2022-legal-population-belgium-was-11584008-inhabitants-0>.

Sturge, G. (2022). Migration statistics. In: House of Commons Library. Disponível em: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/sn06077/#:~:text=Migrants%20living%20in%20the%20UK,people%20who%20were%20born%20abroad>.

World Economics. (2022). The Global Authority on Geographic Investability. United States-Mexico-Canada Agreement (USMCA). Disponível em: <https://www.worldeconomics.com/Regions/USMCA>.

Trading blocs:

ASIA, AFRICA AND OCEANIA

This summarizes all the blocs consulted in the report, considering their political and economic weight globally.

| RCEP/ASEAN

The Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP) is a free trade agreement proposed in Asia-Pacific. Today, it is the world's largest trading bloc, comprising 15 different economies. The bloc is recent, as the agreement to form it dates back to 2020 since negotiations began in 2012. However, the countries in this region already maintained relations through the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), which has existed since the 1960s. This partnership is also known as the ASEAN Plus Six. From this partnership emerges the block known as RCEP. Among the members are the ten ASEAN member countries: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam, and five of the LAC partners in ASEAN: Australia, China, Japan, New Zealand, and South Korea. One of the countries initially defined as "Plus Six," India, was left out, as it opted to withdraw from the RCEP negotiations in 2019. The analysis of this trade bloc is interesting, not only because of its wide scope and global relevance but also because it encompasses several countries on the Asian continent, which concentrated 40% of the world's international migrants in 2019, with more than half of these immigrants still residing on their continent. This motivates us to examine immigration trends and legislation in the region more closely to understand how this phenomenon occurs. In addition, the RCEP also brings together countries from Oceania, a region that in 2019 was already home to 7.7 million immigrants from other regions of the world. This makes the approximation and analysis of the legislation of the bloc and its member countries even more interesting. Finally, the region has specific migratory characteristics, especially women, who represent 61% of the immigrant population in countries like Thailand (MIGRATION DATA PORTAL, 2023a, IOM, 2023, THE ECONOMIC TIMES, 2019).

| AFRICAN UNION

In 2020, the African continent had 25.4 million immigrants and 21 million natives. In this sense, because this phenomenon has a more local aspect, analyzing migratory trends and education initiatives for migrants on the continent more closely seem to be a possibility of diversifying and demystifying knowledge about best practices and policies on our subject. To do this, we delved into the international organization called the African Union, which consists of 55 countries and aims to promote integration between the countries of the African continent in

various areas and aspects. The bloc was founded on May 26, 2001, in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, and launched on July 9, 2002, in Durban, South Africa. It is the successor to the Organization of African Unity - OAU, created in 1963. The organization was modeled on the characteristics of other blocs, such as the European Union and the Commonwealth of Nations. The AU has its own parliament and is particularly active in promoting human rights, democracy, and economic development on the continent. Because of these characteristics, we think the organization can present interesting best practices for dealing with issues such as immigration and education (Mbeki, 2002; IOM, 2021, 2023; MIGRATION DATA PORTAL, 2023b).

| GULF COOPERATION COUNCIL

It is an economic integration organization that brings together six of the eight Persian Gulf countries: Oman, the United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Bahrain, and Kuwait. The GCC, officially established in 1981, comprises countries with common social and economic objectives in the region. Thus, the partnership covers diverse areas such as finance, administration, legislation, tourism, customs, agriculture, scientific collaboration, and industry. Due to the extent of the areas of cooperation and collaboration covered by the Council's Charter and the organization's various agreements, we think that analyzing the approaches given to education with a focus on immigration would be productive, especially in understanding the role that education plays in this model of international cooperation and the region's migratory processes. Currently, migrants make up most of the population in half of the GCC countries, most of which use the kafala system, as mentioned earlier, to receive this population on the move in their territories (MIGRATION DATA PORTAL, 2023c, GCC, 2023; IOM, 2023b).

| COMMONWEALTH OF INDEPENDENT STATES

The Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS, Russian: Содружество Независимых Государств — СНГ), is a regional intergovernmental organization founded on December 8, 1991. It includes 11 of the 15 republics that were formerly part of the Soviet Union: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Kazakhstan, the Russian Federation, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. Georgia and Ukraine were community members in the past, having withdrawn from the council in 2008 and 2014, respectively. The main objectives of the CIS are to maintain the political relations inherited from the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) and to form a Collective Security Treaty. Although its main focus is not internal displacement and immigration in the Community, there are strong migratory movements in the countries that make up the organization, covering both Eastern European and Central Asian countries. This is one of its

main characteristics relevant to the survey, along with its historical character. Russia has the second-largest number of immigrant residents in Europe, with over 11 million residents from various Central Asian countries. In 2019, there were around 5 million Central Asian-born migrants living in the Russian Federation. This characteristic makes it relevant to analyze and survey educational initiatives for migrants in the region.

■ COUNTRIES

Considering the specificities of this large region of the world, we selected seven countries: one from the European continent (Estonia), five from Asia (Lebanon, Turkey, India, China, and Taiwan), and one from Oceania (Australia), as case studies to consider the transitions between these regions.

| India

Despite not being one of the countries with the highest number of immigrants worldwide, India still has almost 5 million residents of different nationalities, more than 200,000 of whom are refugees and 53% of whom are women. In addition, India has been a member state of the IOM (International Organization for Migration) since 2008. For this reason, different projects in various areas focus on migration implemented by the IOM in the country. These projects include the fight against human trafficking and include labor migration and assistance to migrants. Another point that led to the need for a more in-depth analysis of the country and its policies for the education of immigrants and refugees was the consideration that its absence would create a gap in the survey since the country is extremely important for the regions of Asia and Oceania and took part in the negotiations, becoming a trading partner of the RCEP member countries. In this sense, it seems relevant to analyze their immigrant education practices individually and comparatively with those of other countries in the region (IOM, 2023c, MIGRATION DATA PORTAL, 2023c).

| Lebanon

Despite being a country with significant emigration, Lebanon is home to around 1.7 million immigrants and refugees, with a sizable population of Palestinian, Iraqi, and Syrian communities. It does not seem significant at first glance, but it is important to remember that the country has less than 7 million inhabitants. For this reason, we consider it productive to analyze the country in comparison with other Middle Eastern countries, which are included in the GCC survey and which do not have a strong presence of refugees in their migration trends, to understand the reasons why the country is so attractive to refugees in the region and whether part of this phenomenon would be due (or not) to best educational practices for these populations and/or cultural/linguistic proximity (IOM 2023d, MIGRATION DATA PORTAL, 2023e).

| Turkey

Regional conflicts and crises, especially in the Middle East and Africa, have made Turkey both a destination and a transit country for refugees fleeing conflict, poverty, and natural disasters. More than 6.1 million international residents are in the country, 3.5 million of whom are refugees. In addition, in 2016 alone, more than 45 million refugees crossed the country's borders to other places or intended to reside in the country itself. Considering these figures and the fact that Turkey is one of the International Organization for Migration (IOM) main areas of activity, the country is especially relevant for surveying and analyzing best practices in the education of immigrants and refugees (IOM, 2023e, MIGRATION DATA PORTAL, 2023f).

| Estonia

Even though Estonia is theoretically a European country, it was selected for the survey and analysis to compare it with the CIS member states. Estonia is one of the countries that previously formed the USSR and does not participate in the Commonwealth of Independent States. It is also one of the countries with the highest proportional number of immigrants on the European continent. For these reasons, we believe it would be relevant to return our gaze to the continent in this second moment of analysis to understand better the difference between educational practices for immigrants and refugees that may exist due to a different political alignment in the world arena, in this case, thought of in the axis of opposition between the EU and the CIS. The country has almost 200,000 foreign residents among its population of less than 1.4 million, which amounts to 15% of the population. In addition, the country has been a Member State of the IOM (International Organization for Migration) since 2004, and several projects led by the organization have been implemented (IOM, 2023f, MIGRATION DATA PORTAL, 2023g).

| China

It is the largest and most populous country in East Asia and one of the fastest-growing economies in the world. The country projects itself internationally in various fields, such as technology, industry, and science. Approximately 1 million immigrants live in its territory, of which only 38% are women (a contrast to the rest of Asia when we think of countries like Thailand, which has a higher percentage of female immigrants). China is a member state of the IOM (International Organization for Migration) since 2016, having held observer status since 2001. As part of the country's strong and growing involvement in migration policies, it supported and joined the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration (GCM) in 2018. Due to its extremely important role in the

global arena, its immigrant population that is particularly contrasting to the continent, and its active participation in establishing international migration policies, we consider it relevant to carry out a country-specific survey. Taiwan, in a complex relationship with mainland China, has also presented practices that we consider valid for thinking about the relations between the economy, industry, and education as possibilities for renewing and expanding the view of migration (IMF, 2021a; IOM, 2023, MIGRATION DATA PORTAL, 2023h, World Bank, 2005, UN, 2018).

| Taiwan

Due to the One China Policy, Taiwan has complex relations with mainland China, and the rest of the world's actors are aligned with the People's Republic of China. For this reason, Taiwan does not appear individually in statistics from international immigration organizations despite having its distinct policy when contrasted with the migration management of the People's Republic of China. Due to its economic maturity in the 1980s, Taiwan became a destination of interest for migrants from the Southeast Asian region. With a population of approximately 23 million, the territory has more than 300,000 foreign residents, especially Thais, Filipinos, Indonesians, and Vietnamese. For these reasons, we consider it important to highlight some aspects of Taiwanese migration policy to point out these particularities (MFAPRC, 2022; Wang, 2011; Tsay, 2015, Republic of China, 2023).

| Australia

Australia is a southern hemisphere country located in Oceania. With approximately 25 million inhabitants, it ranks 19th among the world's largest economies. The immigrant population living in the country comprises 30.6% of the total population, around 7.7 million people. The number of foreign residents in Australia is considerable. The country is a member state of the IOM (International Organization for Migration), which plays a significant role in international immigration management policies, especially in Oceania. Particularly noteworthy is the country's attention to internal displacement on the continent, such as its involvement through the IOM in climate-related displacement on the Carteret Islands. In addition, "The Economist" mentioned it as the country that receives the most immigrants among the largest countries in the West. For these reasons, we consider it necessary to examine the country's specific policies for the education of migrants and refugees, even though it is also a member of the RCEP bloc.

■ MAIN CONCLUSIONS AND CONSIDERATIONS

Despite some interesting examples, the incipience of this type of study in interdisciplinary studies is confirmed in the case of these three continents. In the context of Africa, Asia, and Oceania, we found some institutions, policies, and a few practices that are considered Open Education, but we did not find many works that consider education for populations on the move, which is strange given that this is a region with large migratory flows. Thus, it would be appropriate to carry out research and practical-didactic work that relates Open Education (its regulations and resources) to the issue of displacement, including the more specific ones mentioned in the survey, thinking about topics such as gender, climate/environment, and class/working conditions. A lack of integration was identified between these areas as a whole, which is most visible in the case of Distance Education, where there would be a possible opening for thinking about Education for Immigrants and Refugees, which, in this context, is more worked on as Education for Academic Mobility/Internationalization or Migration of high-skilled workers.

Thinking about this last point, we again found few compositions aimed at adults, with more documents, legislation, programs, and initiatives for school-age children and adolescents or even for Academic mobility, as mentioned earlier. Adult Education ended up being reduced to a context of Technical and Vocational Training without specifying how it would work with people who have had a migratory experience (in this sense, Australia stands out positively with well-designed programs). In concrete terms, blocs such as RCEP/ASEAN consider education a (re)validation service for diplomas to be provided to the citizens of the member states, similar to the GCC proposal, which thinks exclusively of education for the citizens of the countries that make up the bloc. At the same time, the CIS offers more general educational legislation with some statistics on the presence of migrants in its territory. The bloc that stands out most for producing policies and, to a lesser extent, practices is the African Union due to the conditions of the region it serves and a certain inspiration from the European Union. It's worth noting that documents and initiatives are produced more for refugees than immigrants and that distance learning is seen as a way forward for the development of education (especially at the university level) on the continent, even if it still has connectivity and internet access difficulties. In countries other than Australia, we find best practices and policies, such as India, which has structured Open and Distance Education at various levels of education. However, it does not explicitly consider the issue of migration. Estonia and Taiwan are also

small countries that offer different types of integration via education (Estonia is more for language education, and Taiwan is for technical education). It is also worth mentioning that the countries (China, Australia, India) that are members of the international organizations UN, IOM, and UNESCO presented the most results, indicating the importance of their work in the global context.

As for more specific compositions, we would like to highlight a few. Here, we will articulate the trading blocs with the countries to produce an overview of the most relevant compositions. The African Union, which had the most compositions that fit the scope of our survey, presented policies such as "Continental education strategy for África — CESA" and "The digital transformation strategy for Africa (2020-2030)," which refer to Open and Distance Education, including considering the adult population. In addition, it has gathered the best practices in compositions such as the "Africa Education Innovations Handbook 2020" or even the "OER Initiatives in África," which is run by the UN. It has also established "Pan African Virtual And E-University (PAVEU)" as a higher education institution based on Open and Distance Education precepts. Similar actions regarding HEIs can also be found in Australia with "Open Universities Australia" and in India with "Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU)." In the continent-state, we also find other policies such as "Professional learning for adult educators" for education workers who will serve groups of adults on displacement, offering them various programs: "Humanitarian Settlement Program (HSP)", "Settlement Engagement and Transition Support (SETS)", "The Skills for Education and Employment (SEE)," along with the stipulation of quality standards for working in this area with guidelines such as "National Settlement Outcomes Standards." In India, we have a similar governmental concern with "SWAYAM," but it does not necessarily focus on immigrants but rather on its vast internal migrant population. It works in nine educational areas and produces various developments with regulations such as "Guideline for Developing Online Courses for SWAYAM," which offers guidelines for producing OERs and working in international networks, "Commonwealth Educational Media Centre for Asia (CEMCA)." When thinking about networks, we return to the blocks organized through Distance Education and partially Open Education to serve audiences that may need this educational proposal. Thus, in RCEP/ ASEAN, we find more policies and action plans with "The ASEAN work plan on education 2016 - 2020", "Master plan on ASEAN connectivity 2025", "Roadmap on the ASEAN higher education space 2025" and "Bangkok Declaration on advancing partnership in Education for 2030 agenda for sustainable development in ASEAN," in which the first step is more general plans for Education, then think about plans to increase access to and use of the internet and finally themes such as sustainability and climate change that need to be integrated into educational projects and programs, especially for migrant groups who, according to our survey, are more strongly represented in these three continents. At the GCC, we have more practices such as "Edraak" and "Rwaq," open platforms designed to serve migrants (from the Arab world), especially those on academic mobility. The same can be seen in countries such

as China, which has “Guias de Recepção (Welcome Guides)” with various subdivisions to provide information about the country in a didactic way. The government and universities produce materials such as “XuetangX,” which is used to disseminate best practices from organizations dealing with the issues in question. In Taiwan, we find a similar situation regarding the predominance of best practices with “Cool English” projects that have emerged as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, especially in universities such as the National Taipei University, which has a website entitled “Resources,” in which we have two main areas of activity: “Digital Learning Resources” and “Distance Learning.” The same trend continues in Middle Eastern countries, such as Lebanon with “Kiron,” which was created to be a platform to support Adult Education in this country and beyond, and Turkey, which is again thinking about the sustainability of practices, as reported in “Sustainable approaches to humanitarian assistance in the field of language education for adult refugees in Turkey.” Culturally sensitive education in “Designing Culturally Sensitive Massive Open Online Courses: Learning Culture and MOOCs in Turkey” and “Multicultural Education Curriculum Development in Turkey.” The last country surveyed showed a balance between practices such as “Integration Policy Instruments in Estonia,” which offers different instruments for integrating immigrants, and policies such as “Learner-Centred Education and Adult Education for Migrants in Estonia,” which looks at ways of providing education for adult learners on the migrant theme.

Future work should analyze the compositions more thoroughly and make more connections between different products since we highlight the lack of integration between various types of education and immigrant/refugee audiences. We say this because there are no small numbers of OERs and MOOCs serving countless people in the Global South. Several of these platforms have been integrated into formal education systems, again with government support and guiding policies at the national level that show feedback between best practices and policies, varying the path each country takes to address the issue.

Brazil is close to the contexts of these three continents because it is part of the Global South, with which it shares many of the (un)favorable conditions for developing Open and Distance Education for the adult migrant population. Another parallel is Brazil's participation and articulation with international organizations that deal with migrant issues, such as UNHCR and IOM. This means that Brazil produces more policies and practices and, therefore, has possibilities for comparison and interlinking with other member countries. Like many countries mentioned here, Brazil still lacks many policy compositions at the state or federal level. Following the changes in migration legislation enacted in 2018, these will need to be updated. Further international research is expected to analyze the best public policies in countries whose social, economic, political, and cultural reality is similar to Brazil's.

Considering all that has been mentioned and discussed in this report, we can

conclude that the area of Open Education, in its relation to Distance and Adult Education, thinking of the immigrant/refugee public, needs:

I. more in-depth studies of specific compositions, both political and practical, and other more panoramic studies, making interconnections between the different types of education;

II. research that works intersectionally on issues of gender, class, and race, but also other topics such as human rights and climate change, which profoundly affect countries and the way they prepare to serve groups on the move;

III. surveys, as a state-of-the-art, which would systematize and critically analyze the production carried out in different government spheres (municipalities, state and federal governments, basic and higher education institutions), non-governmental institutions, and for-profit and non-profit companies/organizations;

IV. unifying repositories of different resources and tools and repositories of institutional policies on (inter)national issues and;

V. initiatives that result in events, networks, and programs/action plans that offer more direct guidelines and proposals on how to benefit the adult immigrant and refugee population with the benefits of Open and Distance Education.

■ REFERENCES

Executive Committee of the Commonwealth of Independent States – ECCIS [Исполнительный комитет Содружества Независимых Государств] <https://cis.minsk.by/>

The Economist (2017). Australia admits more migrants than any other big Western country https://www.economist.com/asia/2017/10/05/australia-admits-more-migrants-than-any-other-big-western-country?gclid=Cj0KCQiA8aOeBhCWARIsANRFrQHf2XE7-nM92U47mbmp-omHGM6BE1E4628B3_zz-WRd1x8SXYxrdwaAqBBEALw_wcB&gclidsrc=aw.ds

THE ECONOMIC TIMES (2019). India decides to opt out of RCEP, says key concerns not addressed <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/economy/foreign-trade/india-decides-to-opt-out-of-rcep-says-key-concerns-not-addressed/articleshow/71896848.cms?from=mdr>

The Cooperation Council for the Arab States of the Gulf – GCC (2023). Secretariat General of the Gulf Cooperation Council. <https://www.gcc-sg.org/en-us/Pages/default.aspx>

Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre – IDMC (2023). Pacific Response to Disaster Displacement Project. <https://www.internal-displacement.org/pacific-disasters>

International Monetary Fund – IMF (2021a). World Economic Outlook Database. China. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO/weo-database/2021/October/weo-report-c=924,&s=NGDPD,PPPGDP,NGDPDPC,PPPPC,&sy=2022&ey=2022&ssm=0&scsm=1&sc=0&ssd=1&ssc=0&sic=0&sort=country&ds=.&br=1>

International Monetary Fund – IMF (2021b). World Economic Outlook Database. Australia. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/SPROLLS/world-economic-outlook-databases#sort=%40imfdate%20descending>

International Organization for Migration – IOM (2021). Migration and migrants: Regional dimensions and developments. In: World Migration Report 2022 (M. McAuliffe and A. Triandafyllidou, eds.). IOM, Geneva. https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/WMR-2022-EN-CH-3_1.pdf

International Organization for Migration - IOM (2023a). Asia and The Pacific. <https://www.iom.int/asia-and-pacific>

International Organization for Migration – IOM (2023b). Africa and the Middle East. <https://www.iom.int/africa-and-middle-east#:~:text=Migration%20in%20Africa%20involves%20large,be%20living%20within%20the%20region>

International Organization for Migration - IOM (2023c). Índia. <https://www.iom.int/countries/india>

International Organization for Migration - IOM (2023d). Lebanon. <https://www.iom.int/countries/lebanon>

International Organization for Migration – IOM (2023e). South-Eastern Europe, Eastern Europe and Central Asia . Türkiye. https://www.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd1486/files/documents/south-eastern_europe_eastern_europe_and_central_asia_regional_strategy_2020-2024_6nov20_v05.pdf

International Organization for Migration – IOM (2023f) . Estonia. <https://estonia.iom.int/iom-estonia>

International Organization for Migration – IOM (2023g). China. <https://www.iom.int/countries/china>

International Organization for Migration – IOM (2023h). Australia. <https://australia.iom.int/>

Mbeki, T. (2002). Launch of the African Union, 9 July 2002: Address by the chairperson of the AU, President Thabo Mbeki. https://web.archive.org/web/20090503210549/http://www.africa-union.org/official_documents/Speeches_%20and%20Statements/HE_Thabo_Mbiki/Launch%20of%20the%20African%20Union,%209%20July%202002.htm

MIGRATION DATA PORTAL (2023a). Migration data in South-eastern Asia. <https://www.migrationdataportal.org/regional-data-overview/south-eastern-asia>

MIGRATION DATA PORTAL (2023b). Total number of international migrants at mid-year 2020. África. https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs&t=2020&m=1&rm49=2#:~:text=Migration%20in%20Africa%20involves%20large,be%20living%20within%20the%20region.

MIGRATION DATA PORTAL (2023c). Total number of international migrants at mid-year 2020. Ásia. https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs&t=2020&m=1&rm49=142

MIGRATION DATA PORTAL (2023d). Total number of international migrants at mid-year 2020. Russian Federation. Europe. https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs&t=2020&m=1&rm49=150&cm49=643

MIGRATION DATA PORTAL (2023e). Total number of international migrants at mid-year 2020. Lebanon. https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs &t=2020&cm49=422

MIGRATION DATA PORTAL (2023f). Total number of international migrants at mid-year 2020. Türkiye. https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs &t=2020&cm49=792

MIGRATION DATA PORTAL (2023g) Total number of international migrants at mid-year 2020. Estonia. https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs &t=2020&cm49=233

MIGRATION DATA PORTAL (2023h) Total number of international migrants at mid-year 2020. China. https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs &t=2020&cm49=156

MIGRATION DATA PORTAL (2023i) Total number of international migrants at mid-year 2020. Australia. https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs &t=2020&cm49=36

Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China - MFAPRC (2022). One-China Principle: Anchor for Peace and Stability across the Taiwan Strait. https://www.fmprc.gov.cn/mfa_eng/wjb_663304/zwjg_665342/zwbd_665378/202208/t20220812_10742117.html

Republic of China (Taiwan) (2023). National Statistics. <https://eng.stat.gov.tw/Point.aspx?sid=t.9&n=4208&sms=11713>

Tsay, C.I. (2015). Migration between Southeast Asia and Taiwan: Trends, Characteristics and Implications. *Journal of ASEAN Studies*, 3(2), 68-92. <https://doi.org/10.21512/jas.v3i2.842>

Wang, H.-Z. (2011). Immigration Trends and Policy Changes in Taiwan. *Asian and Pacific Migration Journal*, 20(2), 169-194. <https://doi.org/10.1177/011719681102000203>

World Bank. (2005). Fighting Poverty: Findings and Lessons from China's Success <http://web.archive.org/web/20130922130002/http://econ.worldbank.org/WBSITE/EXTERNAL/EXTDEC/EXTRESEARCH/0,,contentMDK:20634060~pagePK:64165401~piPK:64165026~theSitePK:469382,00.html>

United Nation – UN (2018). Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration. <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N18/451/99/PDF/N1845199.pdf?OpenElement>

I. DETAILING • METHODOLOGICAL

■ PRODUCTION AND MANAGEMENT OF DATA AND METADATA

This production and management, for which we took Freitas (2017) and Krause-Lemke and Puh (2021) as support, consisted of a survey and mapping of legislative and regulatory documents and academic production in the regional, national, and international context, forming a database. To this end, various national and international digital repositories were consulted, depending on the type and form of the information/data presented, such as international organizations (United Nations, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, and International Organization for Migration); trading blocs: European Union, Southern Common Market, Andean Community with its treaties, entities and members, be they: United States Mexico Canada Agreement, North American Free Trade Agreement, Mexico-United States Commission for Educational and Cultural Exchange and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees.

| Americas and Europe

For the first part, the search methodology was carried out using specific markers or search terms for the subject of the report in several languages: Portuguese, English, Spanish, and French. Searching only in English proved insufficient for some markers, even when studying two continents where the use and presence of this language seemed to be greater. Below is an example from the Spanish language (Table 1).

Twenty-eight terms have been combined to meet the subject of this production, such as immigration, migration, education, online, adults, open source, refugee, open education, equity, accessibility, adults, Open Educational Resources, and legislation. Before including the items in the specific survey for each trading bloc and some specific countries in which the issue of migration is more present, the total number of searches for each of the terms or their combinations on Google and Google Scholar, both in English and in the official language of the country/bloc, were surveyed to get a quantitative glimpse of the subject's presence online, noting some limitations. This happens mainly in two contexts:

- A. the use of search languages/countries which, in many cases, create filters in the availability of compositions, limiting our reach and ability to create an exhaustive survey; and,
- B. The blocks' willingness to make results available openly and online for consultation by interested parties may create some gaps in the results.

Table 1. Spanish markers

TERM	SPANISH
1	"(country)" "inmigración"
2	"(country)" "inmigración" "educación"
3	"(country)" "educación" "para inmigrantes"
4	"(country)" "inmigración" "educación abierta"
5	"(country)" "creative commons" "educación"
6	"(country)" "fuente abierta" "educación"
7	"(country)" "inmigración" "educación" "accesible"
8	"(country)" "inmigración" "educación" "equidad"
9	"(country)" "inmigración" "educación" "online"
10	"(country)" "inmigración" "educación" "adultos"
11	"(country)" "fuente abierta" "educación" "inmigrante"
12	"(country)" "refugiado"
13	"(country)" "refugiado" "educación"
14	"(country)" "educación" "para refugiados"
15	"(country)" "refugiado" "educación abierta"
16	"(country)" "refugiado" "educación" "accesible"
17	"(country)" "refugiado" "educación" "equidad"
18	"(country)" "refugiado" "educación" "online"
19	"(country)" "refugiado" "educación" "adultos"
20	"(country)" "fuente abierta" "educación" "refugiado"
21	"(country)" "educación abierta" "legislación"
22	"(country)" "rea" "legislación"
23	"(country)" "inmigrante" "educación" "legislación"
24	"(country)" "refugiado" "educación" "legislación"
25	"(country)" "inmigrante" "educación" "legislación" "rea"
26	"(country)" "refugiado" "educación" "legislación" "rea"
27	"(country)" "migración" "educación"
28	"(country)" "migración" "educación" "recursos educativos abiertos"

Elaborated by: The Authors

In terms of overall results, the number of items selected on this topic also corresponds to the total number of search results for each trading bloc. This means that greater production and availability of materials free of charge and online means a greater supply of good policies and practices to be analyzed and eventually selected. It also allows us to understand how each bloc is dedicated to certain subjects, producing more materials that can be searched for and considered. In this context, the production of the European Union prevails, where the intersection of the three terms “Distance Education,” “Open Education,” and “Adult Education” was more possible to observe and build something that will be visible in the individual presentation of the results. Let's look at some results that corroborate the future citation of specific cases of good policies and practices by showing the numbers for Google's general search engine and, more specifically, Google Scholar.

Table 2. Statistical display of terms "Education" and "for immigrants" (term 3)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
MERCOSUL	530	71.600
EU	29.800	233.000
Andean Community	123	1.570
USMCA	79	3.770
NAFTA	3.920	28.400
Brazil	16.900	297.000

Elaborated by: The Authors
Education Sources: Google and Google Scholar

Table 3. Statistical display of terms "Immigration" and "Open Education" (term 4)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
MERCOSUL	11	1.510
EU	452	15.900
Andean Community	2	185
USMCA	2	32.400
NAFTA	36	5.480
Brazil	343	8.300.000

Elaborated by: The Authors
Education Sources: Google and Google Scholar

Table 4. Statistical display of terms "Immigration," "Education," and "Online" (term 9)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
MERCOSUL	3.760	585.000
EU	135.000	170.000
Andean Community	751	9.830
USMCA	555	97.600
NAFTA	14.200	258.000
Brazil	82.100	5.890.000

Elaborated by: The Authors
Education Sources: Google and Google Scholar

Table 5. Statistical display of terms "Immigration," "Education," and "Adult" (term 10)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
MERCOSUL	1.160	482.000
EU	55.200	3.860.000
Andean Community	311	8.800
USMCA	170	34.000
NAFTA	7.440	729.000
Brazil	54.000	7.290.000

Elaborated by: The Authors
Education Sources: Google and Google Scholar

Table 6. Statistical display of terms "Education" and "for Refugees" (term 14)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
MERCOSUL	1.350	22.200
EU	44.600	1.080.000
Andean Community	356	5.540
USMCA	85	17.300
NAFTA	2.860	67.300
Brazil	22.200	563.000

Elaborated by: The Authors
Education Sources: Google and Google Scholar

Table 7. Statistical display terms "Refugees" and "Open Education" (term 15)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
MERCOSUL	3	757
EU	307	24.600
Andean Community	1	94
USMCA	0	26
NAFTA	9	3.080
Brazil	197	83.600

Elaborated by: The Authors
Education Sources: Google and Google Scholar

We begin our comments on the numerical surveys above by comparing the results between Education for Immigrants (Table 5) and Education for Refugees (Table 6), in which we observed a greater number of results for the refugee theme, indicating a prevalent presence of studies considering this public, a fact that we confirmed in the individual surveys. The high figures for Brazil can be explained by the fact that the searches were made from Brazilian territory, and the Google provider uses this context to carry out the searches, favoring the Portuguese language. In the case of MERCOSUR, compositions were sought in both Spanish and Portuguese, while in the Andean Community, a survey was applied based on the use of Spanish. In the case of NAFTA/USMCA, we use English. We can see that searches referring to online teaching or Distance Education had the most results on Google Scholar, followed by Adult Education, Immigrant Education, and Open Education in last place. This result makes us think about the low quantity of compositions in this world area, which has helped explain the difficulty in finding good policies and practices. We decided to separate the searches by category rather than carry out a single search articulating the areas in question because we noticed a few papers in which the themes of Open, Distance, Adult, and Immigrant/Refugee Education are integrated. A good example of this is Table 7, in which there are blocks with practically non-existent compositions. However, when we carry out searches aggregating markers such as “education” and “migration,” the data in Tables 8 and 9 show the disparity between the number of results for English, Portuguese, and Spanish. Despite this, further statistical studies could help obtain better parameters for future searches for best policies and practices for this population.

Table 8. Statistical display terms "Refugees" and "Open Education" (term 15)

Terms	Google		
	Portuguese	English	Spanish
“educação” “migração”	5.600.000	252.000.000	51.800.000
“educação” “migração” “Brasil”	7.780.000	684.000.000	5.710.000
“educação” “migração” “recursos educacionais abertos”	2.990	430.000	21.500

Elaborated by: The Authors
Education Sources: Google and Google Scholar

Table 9. Statistical visualization terms "Education," "Migration," and "open educational resources" (term 28)

Terms	Google		
	Portuguese	English	Spanish
"educação" "migração"	183.000	4.080.000	397.000
"educação" "migração" "Brasil"	145.000	737.000	115.000
"educação" "migração" "recursos educacionais abertos"	400	3.360	683

Elaborated by: The Authors
Education Sources: Google and Google Scholar

| Africa, Asia and Oceania

For the second part of the report, we analyzed documents from entities such as the United Nations (UN), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), and the International Organization for Migration (IOM); trading blocs: the African Union (AU), the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) and the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), with their treaties, entities, and members: Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP), Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR).

Here, the search methodology was carried out using specific markers or search terms for the theme of this context in several languages: Portuguese, English, Chinese, Russian, and Arabic. Searching in English alone proved insufficient, especially since there are so many countries and trading blocs in which countries do not predominantly use English and do not usually produce texts in this language or translate into it. In this context, we reinforce the importance of studying regions of the world that are not traditionally covered in Brazil when it comes to public policies because they are defined as exotic and distant, classified as oriental most of the time.

Thus, the question of Orientalism (Said, 2007) and the process of linguistic orientalization in Brazil end up creating "images of other cultures and languages as impassable to be articulated with "our" culture, strange and distant as it is. Here, denying or minimizing their existence prevails, eliminating the possibility of contact, conflict, and negotiation" (Puh, 2020, p. 426). Unfortunately, however, this orientalizing effect ends up creating linguistic filters that can affect the collection of good policies and practices that are not linguistically accessible and/or do not appear in search engines used in the West (in Russia, for example, there is "Runet," called the Russian Internet and used by the government. In China, only 2.88% of internet searches in 2013 used Google's search engine,

according to CNZZ, the largest provider of online statistical analysis). Here's a sample using the Russian language (Table 10).

Table 10. Statistical display of terms "Immigration," "Education," and "Online" (term 9)

TERM	RUSSIAN
1	"СНГ" "иммиграция"
2	"СНГ" "иммиграция" "образование"
3	"СНГ" "образование" "для иммигрантов"
4	"СНГ" "иммиграция" "открытое образование"
5	"СНГ" "творческое достояние" "образование"
6	"СНГ" "бесплатный источник" "образование"
7	"СНГ" "иммиграция" "образование" "доступный"
8	"СНГ" "иммиграция" "образование" "беспристрастность"
9	"СНГ" "иммиграция" "образование" "онлайн"
10	"СНГ" "иммиграция" "образование" "Взрослые"
11	"СНГ" "бесплатный источник" "образование" "иммигрант"
12	"СНГ" "беженец"
13	"СНГ" "беженец" "образование"
14	"СНГ" "образование" "для беженцев"
15	"СНГ" "беженец" "открытое образование"
16	"СНГ" "беженец" "образование" "доступный"
17	"СНГ" "беженец" "образование" "беспристрастность"
18	"СНГ" "беженец" "образование" "онлайн"
19	"СНГ" "беженец" "образование" "Взрослые"
20	"СНГ" "бесплатный источник" "образование" "беженец"
21	"СНГ" "открытое образование" "законы"
22	"СНГ" "иммигрант" "образование" "законы"
23	"СНГ" "беженец" "образование" "законы"

Elaborated by: The Authors

In Russia, we combine twenty-three terms to meet the composition theme: immigration, education, online, adults, open source, refugee, open education, equity, accessibility, adults, OER, and legislation. Before including the items in the specific survey for each trading bloc and some specific countries in which the issue of migration is more present, the total number of searches for each of the terms or their combinations on Google and Google Scholar, both in English and in the official language of the country/bloc, were surveyed to get a glimpse, in quantitative terms, of the presence of the subject online, noting some limitations. This happens mainly in two contexts:

A. the use of the search language/country, which, in many cases, creates filters in the availability of compositions, limiting our reach and ability to create an exhaustive survey; and,

B. the blocks' willingness to make results available openly and online for consultation by interested parties, which may create some gaps in the results.

In terms of overall results, the number of items selected on this topic also corresponds to the total number of search results for each trading bloc. This means that a greater production and availability of free and online materials means a greater supply of best policies and practices to be analyzed and selected. It also allows us to understand how each block is dedicated to certain subjects, producing more material that can be searched for and considered. Let's look at some results that corroborate the future citation of specific cases of best policies and practices by showing the numbers for Google's general search engine and, more specifically, Google Scholar.

Table 11. Statistical display of terms "Education" and "for immigrants" (term 3)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
African Union	825	25.000
GCC	329	3.280
RCEP	36	397.000
CIS	630	10.400
Brazil	16.900	297.000

Elaborated by: The Authors

Table 12. Statistical display of terms "Immigration" and "Open Education" (term 4)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
African Union	34	3.920
GCC	11	458
RCEP	3	356
CIS	10	574
Brazil	343	8.300.000

Elaborated by: The Authors

Table 13. Statistical display of terms "Immigration," "Education," and "Online" (term 9)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
African Union	8.290	437.000
GCC	3.470	135.000
RCEP	697	603.000
CIS	3.130	107.000
Brazil	82.100	5.890.000

Elaborated by: The Authors

Table 14. Statistical display of terms "Immigration," "Education," and "Adult" (term 10)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
African Union	3.640	134.000
GCC	1.050	69.100
RCEP	697	603.000
CIS	1.540	68.400
Brazil	54.000	7.290.000

Elaborated by: The Authors

Table 15. Statistical display of terms "Education" and "for Refugees" (term 14)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
African Union	9.270	351.000
GCC	1.590	63.200
RCEP	118	18.200
CIS	2.110	40.000
Brazil	22.200	563.000

Elaborated by: The Authors

Table 16. Statistical display terms "Refugees" and "Open Education" (term 15)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
African Union	32	3.900
GCC	8	443
RCEP	1	228
CIS	9	488
Brazil	197	83.600

Elaborated by: The Authors

Table 17. Statistical display terms "Refugees," "Education," and "Online" (term 18)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
African Union	9.940	574.000
GCC	2.330	81.100
RCEP	314	194.000
CIS	1.890	79.000
Brazil	38.900	2.110.000

Elaborated by: The Authors

Table 18. Statistical display terms "Refugees," "Education," and "Adults" (term 19)

Block/country	Google Scholar	Google
African Union	4.650	540.000
GCC	735	43.300
RCEP	79	160.000
CIS	1.020	46.000
Brazil	28.600	284.000

Elaborated by: The Authors

We began our comments on the numerical surveys above by comparing the results between Education for Immigrants (Table 11) and Immigration and Open Education (Table 12), in which we observed a greater number of results for the topic of Open Education in non-specific Google, especially in the case of Brazil, pointing to a greater presence of Brazilian studies that consider Open Education, a fact that we confirmed in the individual surveys. At the same time, we found, in Google Scholar, also at the Brazilian level, research on the theme of Education and Immigration. This result can be understood as an indication of the consolidation of specific studies in education and immigration, which is broader and more traditional in the country. Studies on Open Education have not yet reached the same degree of intensity, remaining in a more general context of production.

The high figures for Brazil can be explained by the fact that the searches were carried out in Brazilian territory and that Google uses this context to conduct its searches, favoring the Portuguese language. It is also curious to note that in tables 11, 13, and 14, which refer to “Education,” “Immigrants,” “Adults,” and “Online,” there is a greater presence of numbers in general Google in the case of RCEP and, in the case of the African Union, we have a prevalence in Google Scholar, which means that in the case of the AU, there must be more specific studies on this subject. At the same time, in the Asian countries that make up RCEP, more non-academic texts are produced. Table 12 also shows that AU publishes more papers on Open Education in the two Google modalities than RCEP. This data leads us to believe that the theme of this report is more intensively worked on in the scientific sphere on the African continent. We hypothesize that the proximity of the AU to the European Union usually serves as a reference. Furthermore, the conditions in which the countries that make up the AU find themselves mean that Open Education receives greater attention, given that they are large territories with characteristics such as limited access to physical infrastructure and great mobility of the local population due to various economic, climatic, and political factors.

In general terms, we can see that searches referring to online teaching or Online Education had the most results on Google Scholar, considering the three continents (Africa, Asia, and Oceania), followed by Adult Education, Immigrant Education, and Open Education in the last place, which makes us wonder about the low quantity of compositions in this area worldwide. This finding has helped explain the difficulty of determining the best policies and practices for considering open education. Once again, we would like to point out that, in the case of refugees, we found more results in their interface with Online Education, reinforcing the hypothesis we raised in Report 1 when we noted that there are singularities in this group regarding displacement that are better addressed in this area of teaching.

It was decided to separate the searches by category rather than conducting a single search linking the areas in question because we noticed few studies that

integrate Open, Distance, Adult, and Immigrant/Refugee Education. A good example of this is Table 16, in which there are blocks with practically non-existent compositions. In conclusion, more statistical studies could help obtain better parameters for future searches for the best policies and practices for this population and, in comparative terms, demonstrate the specificities of certain continents and their countries/trading blocs.

| Bibliometric and scientometric categorization

We used categorization focusing on the human sciences, supported by Spera Baraldi (2017). This categorization required attention to our database, considering the categories' quantitative and qualitative characteristics. Scientific-political aspects of data design and management were also considered, with a view to future analysis based on this report. Thus, the database was made up of several spreadsheets with descriptive data categorized into the following categories: country/trading bloc; the title of the composition; type of text; period of publication; organizers or authors of the composition; Distance Education Open Education for Adults, checking if there is any reference to any of these last three topics that are central to the report; target audience (immigrants/refugees and/or professionals working in this field); summary description of the composition; access link; and, observations on any specific aspect. The first reflections and observations were drawn from this database and then interpreted and analyzed according to the procedures described below.

| Policy cycle approach

Based on Bowe, Ball, and Gold (1992), the approach adopted allows a better articulation between the three contexts of the policy formulation process observed in the database: the context of influence, the context of the policy's textual composition, and the context of practice. These aspects are analyzed and compared in a comparative approach between the various world and Brazilian contexts. This approach was central to the analysis, as it helped us reflect on and establish a line of reasoning that would allow us to articulate the practices and policies for adult migrants regarding Adult Education and Open and Distance Education, indicating the spheres of influence, modes of textual composition, and practices that feed back into the whole process.

■ REFERENCES

Bowe, R., Ball, S. J., & Gold, A. (1992). *Reforming Education & Changing Schools: case studies in policy sociology*. London: Routledge.

Freitas, C. C. de. (2017). *Gestão do Conhecimento e a formação de professores: percursos e desafios do Observatório de Ideias*. Anápolis: Editora da UEG.

Krause-Lemke, C., & Puh, M. (2021). Produção acadêmica em estudos eslavos no Brasil: balanços e perspectivas para o fomento de novas propostas de cooperação internacional. *Revista Fórum Linguístico*, v.18, n.1, p. 5675-5688.

Puh, Milan (2020). “Tudo junto e misturado?”: as contribuições e os limites do multiculturalismo no ensino de línguas. *El toldo de Astier*, v. 11, n. 20-21, p. 415-432. <http://www.eltoldodeastier.fahce.unlp.edu.ar/numeros/numero20/pdf/Puh.pdf>

Said (2007). *Orientalismo: o Oriente como invenção do Ocidente*. São Paulo: Companhia das Letras.

Spera Baraldi, H. (2017). *Avaliação da produção científica em Ciências Sociais e Humanas: revisão da literatura recuperada em base de dados e rede de autores*. Dissertação (Mestrado). Programa de Pós-Graduação em Ciência da Informação. Universidade de São Paulo (USP).

II. DETAILED RESULTS:
• AMERICAS AND EUROPE

■ ORGANIZATIONS

Three organizations stand out in producing policies and practices on the subject and audience of this report: the United Nations, the International Organization for Migration, and the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization. Their main compositions are presented below.

| United Nations Organization — UN

Five items relevant to the theme of this report were raised, which we present briefly:

I. A strategic document entitled "Refugee Education 2030: a strategy for refugee inclusion," published in 2019, directly addresses Distance Education and Adult Education focusing on refugees. The aim is to promote the conditions, partnerships, collaboration, and approaches that lead all refugee, asylum-seeking returnee, and stateless children and young people and their host communities, including internally displaced people in those communities, to have access to education that enables them to learn, thrive and develop their potential. This document specifically discusses innovations in distance education entitled "Connected Education" between pages 30 and 32. At the same time, on p. 33, it presents the Incheon Declaration, which refers to education for all, including adults.

II. A case study entitled "InterAgency Network for Education in Emergencies: A community of practice, a catalyst for change," commissioned by the Steering Group of the "InterAgency Network for Education in Emergencies (INEE)" itself in 2011, examines Distance Education and Adult Education and documents the changes, the role of INEE, and the concomitant development and growth of the network over time, with a focus on people in humanitarian crises. The aim, therefore, is to promote better collaboration and effectiveness in the context of emergency education for agencies involved in emergency response and post-crisis recovery.

III. The document "Data Transformation Strategy 2020-2025 Supporting protection and solutions" was produced in 2019 by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). It brings together strategies and reports aimed at the refugee population, addressing the three themes of this publication: Distance Education, Open Education, and Adult Education. Reportedly, by 2025, UNHCR aims to be a trusted leader in data and information related to refugees and other affected populations, enabling action that protects, includes, and empowers. This document outlines a strategy for collecting, systematizing, and making data available to facilitate the development of actions for refugee populations, including educational ones. The data types are subdivided into

different fronts, categories, and reports and made available at this [link](#), which contains all the data produced by the Commission.

IV. Another document produced by the UNHCR in 2020 was the report "[Coming together for Refugee Education](#)," in which it was possible to detect a concern with Distance Education and Adult Education. This report on refugee education, dealing with enrollment, families, communities, governments, and violence, allows us to understand that after basic education, the educational options of refugee children decrease dramatically. Factors such as gender, family, and community affect the school life of these children, bringing examples from different regions of the world.

V. The last publication selected in this block, entitled "[The Global Cost of Inclusive Refugee Education](#)", is an article produced by the UNHCR and the World Bank in 2021 and brings economic contributions to thinking about education for refugees, focusing mainly on the non-adult population, as well as extensive information from Distance Education and Open Education to estimate the cost of educating refugee children through inclusive systems in the host country. The data can be used for future studies aimed at adults since best practices and policies have costs that need to be scaled in their preparation and implementation.

| International Organization for Migration — IOM

Among the IOM's compositions, three are worth mentioning.

I. The report "[Education and Migration: an assessment of the types and range of IOM's educational and vocational training projects](#)," published in 2018, deals with the themes of Distance Education and Adult Education aimed at the migrant population. It presents the results of IOM's December 2017 assessment of the current range and types of vocational education and training programs, such as access to basic rights; vocational education, livelihoods, and business development; job skills; migrant training; sustainable development and global citizenship; universities and research; school rehabilitation; scholarships; teacher training and equity. Also noteworthy are the objectives and indicators developed within the UN Sustainable Development Goals Agenda to promote a more holistic approach to the inclusion of migrants in receiving societies.

II. Another IOM report, published in 2022, entitled "[World Migration Report 2022](#)," does not deal specifically with the three major themes of this report but was produced to contribute to a greater understanding of migration and mobility worldwide. It is the eleventh in a series of world migration reports covering the years 2020/2022. This new edition presents important data and information on migration, as well as thematic chapters on highly topical migration issues, with

specific topics such as technology and innovation, the indication of new digital tools for collaboration and the use of artificial intelligence, the contribution of the United Nations, and the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the migrant population.

III. And finally, we mention the tool "Integrating Migration into Education Interventions: A Toolkit for International Cooperation and Development Actors," which was produced in partnership with the EU, UNESCO, and UNICEF in 2022, in which we find important data to be studied with regard to Distance Education and Adult Education. This tool is part of a series of tools developed under the EU's "Mainstreaming Migration into International Cooperation and Development (MMICD)" project. This toolkit aims to provide concise, operational, and easy-to-use information and tools to help international cooperation and development actors integrate migration into education programs and projects. The tools can be understood as procedures for designing a future intervention in the migratory context, such as rapid diagnosis, situational analysis, government policy checklist, stakeholder analysis, problem analysis, risk analysis, theory of change, indicator bank, project design, monitoring, and evaluation checklist.

| United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization — UNESCO

UNESCO stood out in our research with nine compositions that we defined as relevant in the search for best practices and policies.

I. The first composition is the publication "RE Declaration A Declaration 2012," published in 2012 during the World Congress on Open Educational Resources. It does not contain specific information on distance or adult education on displacement. Still, it does provide information and definitions of OER at an international level, which could be explored in the future regarding other compositions.

II. In 2018, the Preliminary report accompanied by a first draft of the Recommendation concerning Open Educational Resources was published. This report emerged from the UNESCO General Conference, which indicated at its 39th session in November 2017 on the direction of international collaboration in Open Educational Resources. It contains information on both Distance Education and Open Education, describing current trends in OER, cultural and linguistic challenges, and the foundations for their inclusive, equitable, and sustainable implementation.

III. The third product selected is the "Sistema de Informação de Tendências Educacionais na América Latina (SITEAL)," a regional observatory founded by the International Institute for Educational Planning, an arm of UNESCO. It

contains information on the project's three priority areas: Distance Education, Open Education, and Adult Education. Its main objective is to systematize and disseminate policies and regulations, statistical indicators, and research on policy implementation to analyze and monitor the educational situation in different areas, such as Education and Technical and Vocational Training and Education and ICT.

IV. Fourthly, we list "Open Educational Resources (OER)", an electronic site maintained by UNESCO on which we can find information on the three priority areas. It contains a selection and systematization of all the Open Educational Resources (OER) and documents relevant to the topic already published by the institution, such as presentations by speakers and the final report of the launch of the OER Dynamic Coalition; an OER guide, guidelines, and program; studies and a forum on the impact of OER; and instruments and support in the context of UNESCO. At the same time, it is necessary to point out a bibliographic research project in Brazil that listed 133 items of academic production in Portuguese on this subject.

V. Here it is worth mentioning the "Diretrizes para Recursos Educacionais Abertos: no Ensino Superior," produced in 2015 by UNESCO and the Commonwealth of Learning, in which it was possible to find data referring to the three topics aimed at higher education and, more specifically, at: governments; higher education institutions; academic staff; student organizations; quality control/certification and academic recognition agencies. These Guidelines outline the topic's main issues and suggest integrating OER into higher education. It aims to encourage government and institution decision-makers to invest in OER's systematic production, adaptation, and use and to bring OER to the center stage of higher education, improving the quality of curricula and teaching and reducing costs.

VI. The next product of interest is the website of UNESCO's "Conselho Internacional para Educação Aberta e à Distância (ICDE)," based in Norway. ICDE is the leading global membership organization working to provide accessible, quality education through online, open, and distance learning. We didn't find any specific information on Adult Education, but we did find a reference to Lifelong Learning, i.e., Continuing Education, with an indication of other priority areas, such as Sustainable Development, internationalization, Quality Education, Policies, technology, OER, Student Success, Celebrating Excellence, leadership in Education, and Research and Innovation.

VII. Another website to be highlighted is "Open Education for a Better World," promoted as a program of the University of Nova Gorica in Slovenia, the Chair on Open Technology for Open Educational Resources and Open Learning and the Center for Knowledge Transfer in Information Technologies of the Jožef Stefan Institute. Again, we find information on Distance and Open Education in it, but no

explicit link to the issue of migration. The international online mentoring program "Open Education for a Better World (OE4BW)" is designed to unlock the potential of Open Education to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals. It offers an innovative approach to building Open Educational Resources, connecting developers of educational materials with volunteer experts as mentors. It is worth mentioning that this program is partnering with the University of Brasilia (UnB), which will become a regional center in 2020.

VIII. The next item, entitled "Language and literacy programmes for migrants and refugees: challenges and ways forward Open Education for a Better World," is academic research that refers to a 2018 program carried out by UNESCO's Global Education Monitoring Team dedicated to the study to the migrant and refugee population, addressing themes in line with the three topics of this report. The article analyzes language and literacy programs for refugees and young adult migrants. It starts from the internationally agreed educational rights of refugees and migrants and analyzes related policies, strategies, principles, structures and standards. A review of available information on the learning outcomes of refugees and migrants indicates significant levels of inequality in host countries.

IX. Finally, in 2019, UNESCO and the Commonwealth of Learning published guidelines entitled "Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies." In them, we find information on the three priority areas but no direct references to Adult Education. These guidelines for policymakers and other stakeholders set out steps for reviewing, analyzing, developing, implementing, and measuring a context-relevant OER policy. They guide but do not determine what governments and actors should do in specific circumstances. Instead, they provide a comprehensive framework for governments and institutions to define a policy vision and scope and then develop a policy master plan.

■ REFERENCES

International Organization for Migration. (2018). Education and Migration: An assessment of the types and range of IOM's education and vocational training projects. Disponível em: <https://publications.iom.int/books/education-and-migration-assessment-types-and-range-ioms-education-and-vocational-training>.

International Organization for Migration. (2022). Migration into Education Interventions: A Toolkit for International Cooperation and Development Actors. IOM, Brussels. Disponível em: <https://publications.iom.int/books/integrating-migration-education-interventions-toolkit-international-cooperation-and>.

Mendizabal, E., & Hearn, S. (2011). Inter-Agency Network for Education in Emergencies: A community of practice, a catalyst for change. Paris, FR: International Institute for Educational Planning. Disponível em: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000212379/PDF/212379eng.pdf.multi>.

Organização das Nações Unidas para a Educação, a Ciência e a Cultura. (2023). Sistema de Informação de Tendências Educacionais na América Latina. Observatório Regional de Políticas de Educação e Primeira Infância. Disponível em: https://siteal.iiep.unesco.org/pt/acerca_de.

Organização das Nações Unidas para a Educação, a Ciência e a Cultura. (2015). Diretrizes para Recursos educacionais abertos (REA) no Ensino Superior. Disponível em <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000232852>.

Organização das Nações Unidas para a Educação, a Ciência e a Cultura. (2012). Declaração Rea de Paris em 2012. Paris, Fr: Congresso Mundial Sobre Recursos Educacionais Abertos (Rea) de 2012. Disponível em: <https://siteal.iiep.unesco.org/pt>.

Organización Internacional para las Migraciones. (2022). Informe sobre las Migraciones en el Mundo 2022. Disponível em: <https://publications.iom.int/books/informe-sobre-las-migraciones-en-el-mundo-2022>.

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2018). Preliminary report accompanied by a first draft of the Recommendation concerning Open Educational Resources. Disponível em: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000265554>.

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2019). Paper commissioned for the 2019 Global Education Monitoring Report, Migration, displacement and education: Building bridges, not walls. Disponível em: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000266077>.

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization & Commonwealth of Learning. (2019). Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies. Disponible em: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>.

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2023). Open Educational Resources (OER). Disponible em: <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-educational-resources?hub=785>.

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. (2019). Refugee Education 2030: A Strategy for Refugee Inclusion. Disponible em: <https://www.unhcr.org/media/38077>.

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. (2019). Data Transformation Strategy 2020-2025: Supporting protection and solutions. Disponible em: <https://www.unhcr.org/media/data-transformation-strategy-2020-2025>.

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. (2020). Coming Together for Refugee Education. Disponible em: <https://www.unhcr.org/media/coming-together-refugee-education-education-report-2020>.

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees & International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank. (2021). The Global Cost of Inclusive Refugee Education. Disponible em: <https://www.unhcr.org/media/39172>.

■ TRADING BLOCS

In terms of trading blocs, those most active on the European and American continents were selected: the European Union; the Southern Common Market — MERCOSUR — whose members are Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, and Uruguay; Venezuela, which is currently suspended; and Bolivia, as a candidate member. The Andean Community consists of the following countries: Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, and Peru. The North American Free Trade Agreement, better known as NAFTA, was created by the United States, Canada, and Mexico. Finally, there is the United States-Mexico-Canada Agreement (USMCA), which, as of 2018, is replacing NAFTA.

| European Union

The European Union is the trading bloc where we found the most composition (25 items) on the subject of this report, with legislation, programs, action plans, courses, educational centers, and repositories that articulate the three types of Education and Migration.

I. We begin with the “Plano de Ação para a Educação Digital 2021-2027,” a synthesis of legislation promoted by the European Union in 2017. This plan promotes innovative, high-quality learning and teaching through new technologies and digital content. The second version of the action plan dates from 2020. It provides guiding principles for reconfiguring education and training systems for the digital age, indicates priority areas and actions, and strengthens cooperation and exchange in digital education at the EU level. It aims at dissemination and international collaboration.

II. In the context of this Plan, one platform born in 2020 is the “European Digital Education Hub,” a learning center that offers resources, opportunities, and training related to digital education, which involves elements of Distance Education, Open Education, and Adult Education. It presents six objectives as a basis for future studies and actions:

- A. support European Union (EU) Member States by setting up a network of national advisory services on digital education to exchange experiences and best practices on the facilitating factors of digital education.
- B. link national and regional digital education initiatives and strategies and connect national authorities, the private sector, experts, education and training providers, and civil society through various activities.
- C. monitor the implementation of the Action Plan and the development of digital education in Europe, including through the results of EU-supported projects.
- D. sharing best practices, contributing to research experimentation, and systematically collecting and analyzing empirical evidence, partly through peer learning.

E. to support cross-sector collaboration and new models for the seamless exchange of digital learning content, addressing issues such as interoperability, quality assurance, environmental sustainability, accessibility and inclusion, and common EU standards for digital education.

F. to support the agile development of policies and practices, acting as a "think and do tank" for digital education and involving stakeholders in user-driven innovation through the "Digital Education Hackathon."

III. It is also worth mentioning the "Eurydice rede europeia de informações sobre sistemas e políticas de educação," promoted by the Council of Ministries of Education, which represents a synthesis of legislation for the network of governmental, non-governmental, and international institutions that aims to research and explain the functioning of the European education system, with a special focus on Distance Education and consultation of EU databases (integrating three databases: UNESCO/OECD/EUROSTAT). The same network has a sítio internet.

IV. An important piece of legislation as a reference for the issue of migration is "The Teaching of Immigrants in the European Union," a document published by the EU parliament in 1997. It defines teaching and teaching practices for immigrants in the bloc. In it, we find three proposals for analysis related to the topic that could be useful for studying policies and legislation: social analysis, political analysis, and legal analysis.

V. We were able to find two more pieces of legislation that are relevant to the scope of this report. The first is entitled "Competências Essenciais para a Aprendizagem ao Longo da Vida," which the Council of the EU promulgated in 2018 as a recommendation to address Vocational Education and Training for Young People and Adults. It addresses the following topics: vocational training, innovation, new educational methods, educational policy, professional qualifications, digital literacy, non-formal education, continuing education, and cooperation in the field of education. The second was defined in 2016 as a recommendation to EU governments under "Upskilling Pathways: New Opportunities for Adults," aimed at Adult Education. It offers additional training pathways to individuals who have not acquired a higher level of formal education. This recommendation comprises three steps: assessing initial skills, offering training opportunities, and validating and recognizing abilities. There are also ways of financing, skills, centers of excellence, and partnership possibilities that receive EU support through various funds: the European Social Fund (ESF), ERASMUS+, the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the Fund for European Aid to the Most Deprived (FEAD), the European Globalization Adjustment Fund for Displaced Workers (EGF), and the European Agriculture Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD).

VI. Next, we present the European Education Area (EEA), which is a set of measures defined for the first time in 2017, whose objective is to build more

resilient and inclusive systems based on the following approaches: improving quality and equity in education and training; teachers, trainers, and school managers; digital education; green education; and, the EEA in the world, addressing all levels of education — from early childhood education to vocational education/training. There is also a section for the Educational Integration of Immigrants and Refugees, focusing on improving quality and equity in education and training in the context of inclusive education, and another section on Distance Education, i.e., Digital Education, with its Action Plan.

VII. In this context was also the “Plano de Ação de Integração e Inclusão 2021 – 2027,” a plan to integrate immigrants in various areas. In the sectoral area of Education and Training, we find more information on the objectives for working with people in a condition of human displacement:

- A. Greater participation of migrant children and children with a migrant background in inclusive, high-quality early childhood education and care facilities.
- B. Teachers should be better equipped with the skills, resources, and support needed to manage multicultural and multilingual classrooms, which would benefit migrant and Indigenous children.
- C. Creation of multi-stakeholder learning communities with the participation of schools, social and health services and parents.
- D. Faster and easier recognition of qualifications obtained in third countries.
- E. Migrants' greater participation in comprehensive language training and civic orientation programs begins when they arrive in the country and accompanies them throughout their integration journey. This line of action also includes the action plan for digital education and a proposal for digital literacy courses for immigrants.

VIII. Another program, which runs from 2021 to 2027 and is already well known in the university environment, ERASMUS+, provides information on Adult Education with a focus on social inclusion and digital transition, thinking of organizations that work with Adult Education. It is also worth mentioning the government program “SIRIUS Rede de Políticas sobre Educação de Migrantes,” which brings together the main stakeholders in migration and education in Europe, including policymakers, researchers, professionals, and representatives of migrant communities who can be activated for future projects and research.

IX. And as a sub-project of SIRIUS and ERASMUS+, between 2016 and 2019, the following was implemented AVOIR, whose three main objectives were to produce:

- A. bilingual materials.
- B. develop teaching skills; and,
- C. create collaborative networks between parents and teachers.

The stages of development were:

- A. study visits.
- B. case studies and summary reports;
- C. implementation studies.
- D. user guide; and,
- E. dissemination.

They were designed to improve the basic mathematical and literacy skills of migrant children and reduce the performance gap between native and non-native students in Europe.

X. Another SIRIUS publication is the report “Towards Inclusive Digital Education for Migrant Children,” published in 2021, which is related to two topics in this report: Distance Education and Open Education, but for non-adult audiences. Specifically, Digital Education is worked on in its inclusive aspect, stipulating inclusive digital pedagogies accompanied by a proposal for educational policies and strategies. In the same vein, between 2020 and 2021, they were coordinated by Belgium's SIRIUS Digital Inclusive Education Workshops, covering nine topics:

- A. Access to digital devices and the internet for refugee and migrant education and digital devices and connections.
- B. Holistic support in education and dialog with policymakers;
- C. Academic and social language in the absence of face-to-face school.
- D. Broader pedagogical, curricular, and educational support for refugees in centers for newly arrived migrants.
- E. Support for parents and their communities.
- F. Teacher support and professional development.
- G. Digital literacy for teachers and students.
- H. New educational technologies.
- I. National digital agenda.

Objectives, challenges/obstacles, policies/solutions, and best practices were indicated for each topic.

XI. The next item is the European School Education Platform, which launches as an OER in 2022 to serve as a meeting point for school agents, officials, teachers, researchers, legislators, and other professionals covering all levels of education, including those relating to initial vocational training and education. It offers the eTwinning program, through which teachers and educators can access project kits, practical examples, testimonials, and an online environment where eTwinners can communicate, create projects, share, and learn together at their own pace, according to their interests.

XII. In addition to the compositions mentioned above, ERASMUS+ supports

other initiatives, such as “Erasmus+ Online Linguistic Support,” which operates in Distance Education and Adult Education. It aims to help individuals integrate into their host society by allowing them to learn the local language.

XIII. Another interesting initiative is “Massive Open Online Courses,” the European Union Commission promoted. The commission commissioned a study assessing the suitability of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) and Free Digital Learning (FDL) for including migrants and refugees. There, you can find language courses, vocational training for children, and higher education, covering the three priority areas that are the focus of this report. The initiative was updated in 2021.

XIV. Another important item in this survey is the “Electronic Platform for Adult Learning in Europe — EPALE,” a program founded by ERASMUS+. EPALE <https://epale.ec.europa.eu/en/why-epale> is an open multilingual network of adult education professionals, including adult educators and trainers, guidance and support staff, researchers and academics, and political agents. You can find MOOCs, OERs, Resource Centers and Sets, Course Catalogs, and Podcasts here. Various forms of collaboration, including Communities of Practice, Discussions, and Partner Searches; and Organizations and modes of contribution: Resources by Theme, Events, Blog, Community Stories, and News.

XV. Regarding the different types of compositions in the context of Distance Education or Digital Education and Open Education, the website “Open Education: OER, OCW, and MOOCs,” maintained by the European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS), provides important characterizations and clarifications about the three types that appear in the title — OER (REA in Portuguese), MOOCs (CMAO in Portuguese), and OCW (Open Course Ware, without translation into Portuguese). In addition, it presents the visions of different political actors and promoters and EU projects.

XVI. Finally, it is worth mentioning the “OER Toolkit,” which aims to provide guidance and information to support staff, students, and other members of the Una Europa community, which consists of 11 European universities, in using and creating OER to extend their work. This is material that is not only freely available online (it meets the demands of distance education) but also has a Creative Commons license (a license that allows copying and sharing that is less restrictive than the traditional ones that indicate “all rights reserved”). Its objectives are:

A. incorporate OER into existing work in education and mobility (e.g., share materials from each through Joint Innovative Formats as OER and create opportunities for students to develop OER as part of their courses and assignments).

B. promote open science, research, and data, as well as open access publications; and

C. incorporate the creation of OER in other areas of activity — such as Future UniLab, Seed Funding initiatives, Staff Weeks, Live My Life, Uma Futura, Student Congress, Una Europa Prize, Una Challenge, and others — to share innovative ideas and results as widely as possible.

| Southern Common Market — MERCOSUR

In the MERCOSUR bloc, among the documents found, we selected five items that will be presented below.

I. The “Educação MERCOSUL” page offers an overview of this bloc's educational rights and benefits. However, there is no mention of Distance or Open Education. However, the topic of “Movement of Persons” is addressed, a term that is close to migration.

II. Here, we can also add the “Documentary Repository,” which contains minutes, agreements, bulletins, decisions, action plans, and treaties related to educational issues in the MERCOSUR Education Sector, which has been coordinating policies since 1991.

III. The same Sector also produces “MERCOSUR education statistical indicators,” the result of the joint work of the member states in the Indicators Working Group (GTT), which began in 1996 and ended in 2014, to which the “MERCOSUR System of ICT Indicators in Education” is aligned, which produced data between 2009 and 2013, with data and categories that can inspire future surveys of this type.

IV. Then there is the report “MERCOSUL: estrutura e agendas,” published in 2015 by the MERCOSUR Secretariat and Technical Advisory Sector. The report discusses the creation of MERCOSUR and its agendas and sets out all the agreements made up to the time of publication. Regarding this report, information on education was found on page 27 and academic exchange on page 33, but there is no mention of migrants and refugees.

V. In practical terms, we found the “Edital para a Contratação de uma Consultora e/ou Instituição Educacional,” promoted in 2022 by the Paraguayan Ministry of Education, in which it was possible to identify a discussion about Distance Education. The project aims to carry out a collaborative and participatory event of creativity, innovation, and prototyping with students from technical courses in Vocational Technical Education in the bloc countries. It consists of two main components: e-learning training courses for teachers and students and executing the collaborative event in hybrid mode.

VI. Still, in Latin America, the Open Education Consortium, a global network focused on Open Education that brings together researchers and educators

working on this issue, is worth mentioning. The Latin American region is listed as its hub under the name Open Education Latin America — OELATAM. It aims to meet the unique needs of the Latin American region by sharing ideas, projects, and experiences and identifying challenges, needs, and areas for possible collaboration. Finally, among the general objectives, the aim of sharing, curating, localizing, and translating Open Educational Resources (OERs) is maintained.

| Andean Community

In the context of the Andean Community, six items were found that fit the proposal of this report.

I. The first is the document “Enseñanza de Integración en los Países Andinos,” published in 2006 by the General Secretariat of the Andean Community. We find mentions of Distance Education and ICTs (p.52) and Open Education (p.49), concerned with promoting cooperation between member states. In its general line No. 3, you can find the topic Migration and Human Mobility, which mentions the recently approved Andean Migratory Statute. It includes a discussion of terminology, general guidelines outlining basic rights, and other relevant information.

II. Another document that can be useful in best policy studies is the “Normas sobre Migración en la Comunidad Andina,” published in 2018 by the General Secretariat of the Andean Community, which brings together all the Community's laws and regulations on migration.

III. Em terceiro lugar, podemos destacar a apresentação “Comunidad Andina: Situación actual y principales desafíos”, publicado em 2009, enquanto publicação Diretora Geral da Secretaria Geral da Comunidade Andina. It provides information about several community projects, two of which are closer to our themes: “Educación Intercultural bilingüe en contextos de diversidad cultural em frontera Ecuador Perú” e “Proyecto Calidad y Equidad en la educación: Red andina para el desarrollo en las ciencias, matemática y la comunicación — EDUCIMAC.”

IV. EDUCIMAC has existed as a specific project since 2011. It is an educational project aimed at disseminating education to non-migrant students in mainstream schools but with information and reflections on Distance Education. Its objectives are:

A. locate, evaluate, and adapt tested teaching materials with open source and open access.

B. develop and test educational materials and resources, as well as a collaborative strategy based on ICTs; and

C. convene the educational institutions that will test activities to update teachers on using ICTs, evaluation strategies, and implementing the Latin American Network.

V. In 2008, the Subregional Council of Andean Workers published a document entitled “Un análisis a la Migración Laboral entre los países de la CAN incluido Venezuela” (An analysis of labor migration between CAN countries, including Venezuela). The document focused on the study of labor migration in the community and presented the educational objectives of the Andean Community.

VI. Finally, we can mention the decision, that is, the law, “Apoyo a la cohesión económica y social en la CANCESCAN II,” which has existed since 2010 and was enacted by the Andean Council of Ministers of Foreign Affairs. With it, a bi-national project of the Andean Community and the European Union entitled “Support for economic and social cohesion in CANCESCAN II” was set up, in which one of the cross-border sub-projects implemented interested us: “Frontera PerúEcuador: Educación Intercultural en contextos de Diversidad Cultural y Lingüística de la provincia de frontera de San Ignacio en el Perú y de Zamora Chinchipe de Ecuador” since it involves education and the border context which usually involves reflections on migrations or movement of people.

| North American Free Trade Agreement — NAFTA and United States-Mexico-Canada Agreement — USMCA

Regarding these two blocs, more information could not be found that could be included in this report since the issue of migration is not covered in either of the two treaties/agreements. More information can be found in specific legislation or institutions, such as the Mexico-United States Commission for Educational & Cultural Exchange (COMEXUS), an organization created by the US and Mexican governments to finance education studies in the US. There, you can find studies on migration and adult education. In addition, more data could be obtained from the specific analysis of the United States, Mexico, and Canada, which will be presented in the Countries block.

■ REFERENCES

Armalys, T., Sanchez, P. M. R., Graaf, L. (2021). Sirius Watch 2021 Towards Inclusive Digital Education for Migrant Children. Bruxelas: SIRIUS. <http://donboscointernational.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Sirius-watch-202114.pdf>

Bautista, J. S., Reyes, G. M., García, D. M. (2008). La situación socio-laboral en la subregión Andina: Un análisis a la Migración Laboral entre los países de la CAN incluido Venezuela. Bogotá: Confederación de Sindicatos Cristianos de Bélgica, Instituto de Educación Obrera Internacional. https://www.ituc-csi.org/IMG/pdf/La_situacion_socio-laboral_en_la_subregion_andina.pdf

Bekemans, L. (1997). The Teaching of Immigrants in the European Union. Luxembourg: European Parliament. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/workingpapers/educ/pdf/100_en.pdf

Comissão Europeia. (2020). Comunicação da Comissão ao Parlamento Europeu, ao Conselho, ao Comité Económico e Social Europeu e ao Comité Das Regiões. Plano de Ação para a Educação Digital 2021-2027: Reconfigurar a educação e a formação para a era digital. Bruxelas: European Commission. <https://education.ec.europa.eu/pt-pt/focus-topics/digital-education/action-plan>

Comissão Europeia. (2020). Comunicação da Comissão ao Parlamento Europeu, ao Conselho, ao Comité Económico e Social Europeu e ao Comité Das Regiões. Plano de ação sobre a integração e a inclusão para 2021-2027. Bruxelas: European Commission. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/en?file=2020-11/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf

Comissão Europeia. (2013). Comunicação da Comissão ao Parlamento Europeu, ao Conselho, ao Comité Económico e Social Europeu e ao Comité Das Regiões. Abrir a Educação: Ensino e Aprendizagem para todos de maneira inovadora graças às novas tecnologias e aos Recursos Educativos Abertos. Bruxelas: European Commission. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/PT/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52013AE6185>

Comunidad Andina. (2021). Decisión 878. Estatuto Migratorio Andino. XXVI Reunión Ordinaria del Consejo Andino de Ministros de Relaciones Exteriores de la Comunidad Andina. <https://www.comunidadandina.org/DocOficialesFiles/Gacetas/Gaceta%204239.pdf>

Comunidad Andina. (2018). Normas sobre Migración en la Comunidad Andina. Lima, Peru: Secretaría General de la Comunidad Andina. <https://www.comunidadandina.org/StaticFiles/201832185827normasmigracion.pdf>

Comunidad Andina. (2010). Decisión 744. Proyecto de Cooperación CANUE: “Apoyo a la Cohesión Económica y Social en la Comunidad Andina - CESCAN II”. Décimo Octava Reunión Extraordinaria del Consejo Andino de Ministros de Relaciones Exteriores.

<https://www.google.com/url>

[sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwihz8WAx7yCAxV6JrkGHTMHCUoQFnoECA0QAQ&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.comunidadandina.org%2FDocOficialesFiles%2Fdecisiones%2FDEC744.doc&usg=AOvVaw0slw1ldzrgMtWFJVsOd8u1&opi=89978449](https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwihz8WAx7yCAxV6JrkGHTMHCUoQFnoECA0QAQ&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.comunidadandina.org%2FDocOficialesFiles%2Fdecisiones%2FDEC744.doc&usg=AOvVaw0slw1ldzrgMtWFJVsOd8u1&opi=89978449)

Mercosul. (2015) Mercosul: Estructura e Agendas. Montevideo.

<https://www.mercosur.int/pt-br/quem-somos/organograma-mercosul/>

Mora, E. A. (2006). Enseñanza de Integración en los Países Andinos. Lima: Comunidad Andina.

https://www.comunidadandina.org/StaticFiles/201166172212libro_ensenanza.pdf

União Europeia. (2016). Recomendação do Conselho de 19 de dezembro de 2016 sobre percursos de melhoria de competências: novas oportunidades para adultos. Bruxelas: Jornal Oficial da União Europeia. [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/PT/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016H1224\(01\)&from=BG](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/PT/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016H1224(01)&from=BG)

União Europeia. (2018). Recomendação do Conselho de 22 de maio de 2018 sobre as Competências Essenciais para a Aprendizagem ao Longo da Vida. Bruxelas: Jornal Oficial da União Europeia. [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/PT/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018H0604\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/PT/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018H0604(01))

União Europeia. (2022). Inclusive Digital Education Workshop For Migrants and Refugees: 2-3 December 2020, 22-23 April 2021. Bruxelas: SIRIUS.

<https://www.sirius-migrationeducation.org/digital-education/>

■ COUNTRIES

Regarding North American countries, 18 items were found in Canada, 13 in the United States, and 4 in Mexico, with two additional joint items: Mexico and the USA. Finally, we also present the results found for Brazil, of which there were 11.

| Canada

Canada presents a variety of materials (reports, guides, courses) and regional and national policies on Adult Education, Distance Education, and Immigrant Education, totaling 18 elements in our selection.

I. We begin with the report “The development and State of the Art of Adult Learning and Education (ALE),” produced in 2008 by the Council of Ministers of Education of Canada and the Canadian Commission for UNESCO. This report offers a State of the Art that was originally the result of UNESCO's 6th International Conference on Adult Education, which discussed, at different times, the theme of education for immigrant adults. It includes surveys and polls, tables of activities and programs focused on Education, Literacy/Literacy, and Additional Languages, and indications of best practices.

II. Global Affairs Canada's “Together for Learning” campaign from 2021 to 2023 is another interesting production. This campaign aimed to promote quality education for refugee children and young people through four areas of action:

- A. Program Excellence;
- B. Diplomatic involvement.
- C. Amplifying Local Voices and Building the Evidence Base.

III. We continue with the guide “Life After War: Education as a Healing Process for Refugee and War Affected Children,” a manual published in 2012 by the School Programs Division of the province of Manitoba. This guide is aimed more at non-adult audiences but provides for work with families. The guide was produced to help education professionals deal with refugee children who have faced war. It contains not only definitions of certain terms and types of trauma but also suggestions for activities and some school checklists.

IV. We have also selected the “Newcomer Introduction to Classes Online (NICO)” course, promoted by The Immigrant Education Society (TIES), aimed at Canadian citizens, residents, refugees, or “protected” persons. As a free online course, it works on computer skills, online communication, study skills, and vocabulary. It is funded by Immigration, Refugees, and Citizenship Canada,

which facilitates the arrival of immigrants, offers protection to refugees, and offers programming to help newcomers settle in Canada. It promoted digital literacy, with a view to including students who want to take online courses through the Society but don't have computer skills.

V. Another course relevant to our theme is "LINC Home Study," promoted by the abovementioned Society. Its target audience is Canadian citizens, residents, refugees, or "protected persons" who cannot attend face-to-face classes. It offers a diverse range of courses and classes, such as free English lessons, classes and activities on the platform, and a weekly meeting with an instructor for guidance and questions at intermediate to advanced levels. The free online course allows for some distance learning and open education, but there are some restrictions regarding location. At LINC, basic classes are only available in person. There is another type of course called "LINC Blended," i.e., a hybrid course in which the student has mostly online lessons and exercises plus a 3-hour face-to-face meeting during the week, again covering intermediate to advanced levels. The course is free, but classes are limited to those in Calgary who can access the Society's building, where face-to-face classes occur.

VI. The Immigrant Education Society offers adult training courses on its online language course platform, Learn English. "English for Employment: Job Search (EEJS)," provided on the same platform as an online course, deals with applying for jobs in Canada, with CV content, filling in forms, preparing for interviews, etc.

VII. The latest of these courses offered by the Society is the "Workplace Online Retention Class (WORC)," an online course on the TIES platform to promote communication skills in the workplace. It is free, suitable for intermediate and advanced levels, and includes language and soft skills training. It aspires to help you succeed in the Canadian workplace.

VIII. The Society itself prepared the Guide, which meets the requirements of Distance and Open Education regarding Education for Migrants and Refugees of all ages and levels. It is designed in the different languages of the main communities present on Canadian territory.

IX. In addition to English courses, there are similar French courses, such as "Cours de langue pour les immigrants au Canada — CLIC," organized by Le Collège Éducacentre, a French-speaking college in British Columbia. Its target audience is people over 18, permanent residents, and people protected under section 95 of the Immigration and Refugee Protection Act. However, they cannot register with LINC. It offers levels 1 and 2 of the French course and is funded by the Canadian government. This course is also provided specifically for immigrants and refugees in Canada.

X. In this context, it is also worth mentioning "Amélioration du français," a

collection of resources maintained by the Centre Collégial de Développement de Matériel Didactique. Its target audience is people with access to the Internet who are learning French. The list includes printable resources, alternative materials, and links to other content.

XI. In 2021, Immigration, Refugees and Citizenship Canada prepared the manual “Découvrir le Canada: les droits et responsabilités liés à la citoyenneté”. It is a study guide to prepare for the test used to obtain Canadian citizenship. It explains history, citizenship systems, economics, etc. Something similar can be found under the name “Guide for Newcomers to Newfoundland and Labrador,” a guide for immigrants with basic information about Canada, obtaining documents, and first steps promoted by the Association for New Canadians. Both guides meet the requirements of Distance Education and Open Education, designed for adult audiences.

XII. Along these lines, it is important to mention the “Best Practices in Settlement Services” website created and maintained by Immigration, Refugees, and Citizenship. It offers everyone access to the Internet information on the main programs for the immigrant community in Canada. Its two main objectives are:

A. present best practices in settlement services to inform organizations, governments, and individuals working with newcomers about the programs being carried out in Canada and worldwide, divided into Information and Orientation, Language, and Skills; Access to the Labor Market, Welcoming Communities and Development of Policies and Programs.

B. also aims to promote innovative ways of helping immigrants integrate into their new communities through referrals.

XIII. It is also worth mentioning the workshops and programs promoted by the Immigrant Settlement & Integration Program — SUCCESS. A range of workshops is available to students with internet access. The online workshops discuss services and programs for immigrant integration, English teaching, and jobs.

XIV. Finally, in addition to the proposals for immigrant/refugee integration, Canadian public bodies also promote activities prior to displacement, with a view to a more conscious and informed arrival in the country. Thus, the Government of Canada, through its Canadian Orientation Abroad program, in partnership with the International Organization for Migration (IOM), has produced the “Refugee Orientation Handbook,” available in several languages, and aims to inform potential immigrants about life in Canada.

| United States of America

In this country, we found predominantly legislation and materials with practical information and explanations of migration policies, comprising 13 items.

I. We begin with the law “Part 100 - nondiscrimination under programs receiving federal assistance through the department of education effectuation of title vi of the civil rights act of 1964,” enacted in 1980, used to guarantee any immigrant access to education, regardless of their legal status. Here, we find interesting information on Open Education and Adult Education from sections entitled “Illustrative Applications,” which are presented as sections where the legislator himself suggests ways of applying certain elements of the law. Aspects of training or professional/vocational education are also extensively commented on and discussed in the law, for which examples are again given as to how the legal guidelines should be applied in concrete situations.

II. Another law of interest is the “Emergency Immigrant Education Program,” presented as a government program of the Ministry of Education, with Offices for Elementary and Middle School Education. In it, we find guidelines that try, in various ways, to organize a government program that acts in more immediate and emergency moments so that the immigrant can be welcomed.

III. Regarding practices, it is worth mentioning the “USA Learns” course, promoted by the Department of Education of the City of Sacramento, which contains elements of this report's three themes. This is a free online course in English as a foreign language — a course for citizenship and professional skills v the so-called “job skills” (Skills for the Nursing Assistant).

IV. In addition to this course, we can list several productions of materials, mostly guides, such as the “How do I Guides,” produced by the Citizenship and Immigration Service, which deals with immigration issues, including various groups that are on the move: American citizens, permanent residents, non-immigrants, refugees and asylum seekers and employers, presenting practical information, including in several languages of the world in its Multilingual Resource Center.

V. The same service has produced two more guides: 1) “Welcome to the United States: A Guide for New Immigrants” from 2015, which provides information about daily life in the United States and some basic civic information focused on immigrants and is available in 14 languages.

VI. 2) the “USCIS Welcomes Refugees and Asylees Brochure,” issued in 2019, provides information on rights, responsibilities, and the importance of US citizenship. It is aimed at refugees and asylum seekers and is available in 17 languages.

VII. In 2021, the Northwest Regional Educational Laboratory produced another guide entitled “Helping Newcomer Immigrant and Refugee Students Register for Secondary School,” aimed at education professionals who receive immigrant or refugee students. The guide contains an infographic on registering and adapting immigrant and refugee children in US schools and information on assisting their parents. It can be useful for education professionals, immigrants, and refugees who want to learn more about school registration processes.

VIII. Another guide that meets the requirements of Distance Education and Open Education but is not exclusively focused on adults is the “Resource Guide: supporting undocumented youth,” published by the US Ministry of Education in 2015, to gather information on how to deal with undocumented children and adolescents. It includes legislation, resources, models, and tips for educators and educational institutions, including advice for Higher Education Institutions and educational programs aimed at Adult Education funded by the federal government (p.44).

IX. In practical terms, we can mention websites such as “United We Dream,” which results from the work of the “Immigrant Youth” network, the largest network that brings together young people who think about immigrant issues. It contains resources for immigrants, such as legal information and legal assistance. It also provides guides on topics of interest (e.g., a list of consulates and updates on immigration policies, especially DACA—Deferred Action for Childhood Arrivals).

X. Another site with a similar proposal is “The Dream: Resources,” run by The Dream Network. It brings together young professionals who have had the opportunity to obtain a university degree despite entering the country young and undocumented. The page brings together various resources for immigrants — especially undocumented immigrants. It provides legal information on scholarships, health, etc., within Distance and Open Education parameters.

XI. The website “Immigrant Rising: Resources” is also highlighted here because it was launched by a non-governmental organization in 2006. Again, it focuses on undocumented immigrants and professionals who can work with them. It provides a list of resources on law, entrepreneurship, and higher education, such as institutional practices, ways of entering universities, and using art for empowerment.

XII. The last site to mention is the “National Immigration Law Center,” a non-governmental organization that has existed since 1979 and provides legal information for immigrants on COVID-19, labor rights, education, taxes, and other related issues. In it, we also find specific tools for post-secondary education, data on the social and economic impacts of improving access to higher education for immigrant students, and ways social agents can facilitate and enhance access for immigrants.

| Mexico

In this country, there are slightly fewer compositions focused on some of the aspects dealt with in this report — 4, as well as two compositions that interface with the United States.

I. First, let's introduce the "Fundación Carlos Slim," a non-profit organization founded in 1986 that helps vulnerable populations in various areas, including education. Its website has a range of courses for immigrants in the US or returning to Mexico, from legal support to training courses for adults and education for children and adults. Another highlight is the site's six platforms, which focus on digital inclusion, open education, and lifelong learning.

II. In terms of the interface, it is worth mentioning "¡Elige, aprende y supérate!: guía educativa para mexicanos en el exterior y en retorno", a guide produced by four Mexican public bodies: the Secretariat for Foreign Affairs, the Secretariat for Public Education, the Institute for Mexicans Abroad, and the National Institute for Adult Education. In it, migrants will find the options to complete, continue, and/or enrich their distance learning studies in Mexico, such as teaching materials, scholarships, revalidation of studies, digital options, technical courses, and careers from basic to upper secondary and higher education.

III. The aforementioned National Institute for Adult Education has prepared the "Educación sin Fronteras," program, which aims to provide primary and secondary education to immigrants, refugees, and returned or repatriated Mexicans, with a special focus on distance education.

IV. In 2019, the new General Education Law was approved. The first ten articles of the law provide information on open and free education, with article 9 being especially interesting: "Art. 9 (V): Disseminate and, where appropriate, promote various educational options, such as open and distance education, through the use of digital platforms, educational television and information, communication, knowledge, and digital learning technologies."

V. In legal terms, we would also highlight the "Convênio COMAR," promoted in 2018 by the "Comisión Mexicana de Ayuda a Refugiados" — COMAR and the "Instituto Nacional para Educação de Adultos." This agreement is based on collaborative work on refugee education, emphasizing reducing illiteracy among refugees and adult education. It serves as an example of how different bodies can work together.

VI. Finally, "Universidad Abierta y a Distancia de México," which has existed since 2012 and is under the care of the Ministry of Public Education. It emerged after the "World Conference on Higher Education for the Twenty-first Century: Vision and Action" in 1998, which led the government to create a Master Plan for

Open and Distance Higher Education, proposing the creation of collaborative networks and programs to train staff to work in this area of education. It currently has Basic, Disciplinary, and Specialized Training Centers, which include undergraduate and postgraduate courses.

| Brazil

Finally, we provide information on how the subject of this report has developed in Brazil. The results to be presented here add to what is already included in the section on MERCOSUR. It is necessary to consider the broader reality of this trading bloc and the specificities of this country, the largest in Latin America. Most of the compositions result from the work of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and some public bodies, with 11 compositions selected in total.

I. We began with legislative issues, citing the “National Education Plan,” sanctioned in 2014 and valid until 2024, in which Open Educational Resources have found their place, with three contributions to the final text, included in 2 of the 20 goals set out in the document:

A. goal 5: make all children literate by the end of the third year of elementary school at the latest;

5.3) Select, certify, and disseminate educational technologies for children's literacy, ensuring the diversity of methods and pedagogical proposals, as well as monitoring the results in the education systems in which they are applied, and they should preferably be made available as open educational resources; and,

B. Goal 7: Promote the quality of basic education in all stages and modalities, improving school flow and learning to achieve the following national averages for IDEB:

Table 1. National measures for IDEB

IDEB	2015	2017	2019	2021
Early years of elementary school	5,2	5,5	5,7	6,0
Final years of elementary school	4,7	5,0	5,2	5,5
High school	4,3	4,7	5,0	5,2

Fonte: INEP

7.11) Select, certify, and disseminate educational technologies for early childhood education, primary education, and secondary education, ensuring the diversity of teaching methods and proposals, with preference for free software

and open educational resources. Monitor the results in the education systems where they are applied.

7.13) Implement the development of educational technologies and innovation in teaching practices in education systems, including open educational resources, to ensure improved school flow and student learning.

II. Thus, we see that this issue has received some attention more recently in the country. However, it still requires many other contributions for its implementation to become visible, as was the case with Decree No. 52.681 of September 26, 2011, of the city of São Paulo, which deals with the "licenciamento obrigatório das obras intelectuais produzidas com objetivos educacionais, pedagógicos e afins, no âmbito da rede pública municipal de ensino (compulsory licensing of intellectual works produced for educational, pedagogical and related purposes, within the scope of the municipal public education network)" that must be done to be freely used. More studies need to be done on OERs, as Santos (2013) did in the book "Recursos Educacionais Abertos no Brasil: o Estado da Arte, desafios e perspectivas para o desenvolvimento e inovação".

III. Among the UNHCR's compositions, we can highlight the preparation of newsletters, booklets, and websites, such as:

A. "Cartilha para refugiados no Brasil," published in 2018, provides information on various practices and policies supported and implemented by the agency: goodwill ambassadors and special envoys, Brazil's declaration and action plan, a Help platform, protection and integration mechanisms, etc. The document aims to provide information on the rights of refugees in Brazilian territory, covering a wide range of dimensions, such as education, health, religion, etc.

B. "Cartilha de Informações Financeiras para Migrantes e Refugiados (Financial Information Booklet for Migrants and Refugees)" is a booklet launched in 2022 that focuses on aspects of Open Education. The document's main purpose is to inform refugees about where they can access the information they need to enable them to enter the Brazilian labor market. It lists several initiatives on distance and open education with different focuses, from learning Portuguese to other trades, including encouraging entrepreneurship.

C. Another booklet produced in 2019 is "Guia de informação sobre o trabalho de imigrantes e refugiados (Information Guide on the Work of Immigrants and Refugees)," which informs the public on how to enter the Brazilian labor market and seeks to train them on their rights and duties.

D. "Passarela: português como língua de acolhimento para fins acadêmicos," a 2020 textbook written for the Portuguese: Práticas Textuais Acadêmicas I and II courses for migrant refugee students enrolled in undergraduate and postgraduate courses at the Federal University of Paraná (UFPR). It is part of a recent trend to

produce teaching materials designed for people on the move but that follow some of the principles of Open Education, Distance Education, and Adult Education. Due to how they are produced and made available, as well as the topics covered, these types of education are close to adult life.

E. “Educação para refugiados” is an electronic website part of the “Projeto do Guia Nacional de Educação para Educadores, Pais, Responsáveis e Crianças Refugiadas no Brasil”. The initiative is available for consultation and is open to being continually fed updated information, content of interest to educators and refugees, and national best practices. On the website, we find the complete guide on the right of access to the public education system (in Portuguese, English, Spanish, French, and Arabic), an interactive map with best teaching practices and initiatives that promote the cultural and social integration of refugees, refugee claimants, and stateless persons, a series of videos on interculturality, and a blog.

IV. We then decided to present two types of maps of interest:

A. “Mapa de Serviços Abertos (Open Services Map),” published in 2020 by the Open Education Initiative (now no longer active), served as a permanent space for inserting and making available information about service providers who worked with the logic and ethics of free software and open educational resources (OER), giving visibility to Brazil's recognized leadership in these two areas. The Open Education Initiative created this website, resulting from cooperation with UNESCO as part of contract ED00283/2020. This contract aimed to provide free and open-access tools for experimentation and use by education stakeholders.

B. The “Observatório Educação Vigiada,” launched in 2021, is today a research group with as its main purpose “the scientific dissemination of academic researchers and social organizations whose objective is to collect and disseminate information on the platformization of public education in Brazil and South America and to encourage a debate in society regarding its social and educational impacts.” The reason for its creation was due to the “perception that the scarcity of information on the actions of large technology companies — especially those that value themselves through the collection, processing, and commercialization of data from users of their digital platforms and services — in the provision of educational technologies and data center space to public institutions, hinders research efforts, public discussion about the risks and the decisions of managers about the future of technologies in their networks and institutions.”

V. Regarding Distance Education, it is worth highlighting the “Censo EaD.BR (EaD.BR Census),” produced by the Brazilian Association for Distance Education (ABED), currently in its eleventh edition in 2018. It consists of mapping Brazil's distance education (DE) scenario and the sector's main trends. Because the partner institutions are doing the mapping on a voluntary basis, there is no

intention of establishing a complete scenario of distance education in Brazil; rather, there is a search for the broadest possible scope. The analyses allowed for a series of categorizations and data: the panorama of market trends, categories of institutions working with distance education, the types of courses offered, the public benefits, the form of execution, and the administrative organization of this modality.

VI. With this census, it is worth presenting the “[Escolha Livre](#)³ (Free Choice)” website, produced at the University of Brasilia by the UNESCO Chair in Distance Education. This website meets the three thematic requirements of this report. This guide, aimed at researchers and the public, proposes a range of free, open options and strategies to help the school community and its agents plan medium- and long-term strategies. The website provides tools, systems, and platforms essential for reflecting on Open Education and promoting quality, inclusive, and equitable education in today's digital culture. Particularly interesting to mention are Wikimedia Commons, which archives different resources for future free consultation; the Internet Archive, where you can find free content; and MEC RED, which works as a repository and social network for teachers, bringing together MEC educational resources in one place (Teacher's Portal, International Bank of Educational Objects and Public Domain). Three free platforms are also listed: BigBlueButton or Mconf, Jitsi, and Mumble, each with its specific features and services, and platforms for collaborative writing: Etherpad, OnlyOffice, and Wikiversity. Finally, the site offers a list of OERs according to categories: photos and images, videos, sounds and music, educational, and various. These are free and open resources for consultation and use.

³ The version studied in the report predates the update made to the Escolha Livre website and the change of name of our Chair in 2024, but the analysis remains relevant.

■ REFERENCES

Freitas, A. et al. (2020). Passarela: português como língua de acolhimento para fins acadêmicos. Curitiba, PR: Editora Peregrina. https://www.acnur.org/portugues/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Passarela_Portugues-como-lingua-de-acolhimento-para-fins-academicos.pdf

Alto-comissariado das Nações Unidas para os Refugiados - ACNUR. (2021). Guia para pais e educadores sobre integração de crianças e adolescentes refugiadas nas escolas. https://educacaoeterritorio.org.br/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/5a0238_c0428c900687484c884c6ddf7096d2bd_compressed_compressed.pdf

Alto-comissariado das Nações Unidas para os Refugiados. (2018). Protegendo Refugiados no Brasil e no Mundo. https://www.acnur.org/portugues/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Cartilha-Institucional-Final_site.pdf

Brasil. (2014). Lei nº 13.005/2014. Aprova o Plano Nacional de Educação – PNE e dá outras providências. https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2011-2014/2014/lei/l13005.htm

Canadá. (2012). Life After War: Education as a Healing Process for Refugee and War-Affected Children. Government of Manitoba. https://www.edu.gov.mb.ca/k12/docs/support/law/full_doc.pdf

Council of Ministers of Education, Canada. (2008). The Development and State of the Art of Adult Learning and Education (ALE). Toronto, Ontario. <https://www.cmec.ca/Publications/Lists/Publications/Attachments/194/FINAL%20CONFINTEA%20VI%20EN.pdf>

Estados Unidos Mexicanos. (2019). Ley General de Educación. Nueva Ley publicada en el Diario Oficial de la Federación el 30 de septiembre de 2019. <https://www.salud.gob.mx/unidades/cdi/nom/compil/130793.html>

Instituto Migraciones y Derechos Humanos (IMDH). (2019). Guia de Información sobre Trabajo a los Inmigrantes y Refugiados. https://www.migrante.org.br/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/IMDH_cartilha_PT-ES_compressed.pdf

México. (2018). Guía Educativa: Elige, Aprende y supérate. Secretaría de Relaciones Exteriores, Secretaría de Educación Pública. <https://ime.gob.mx/educacion/programa/guia-educativa-ime-para-mexican-s-en-el-exterior>

Ministre de Citoyenneté et Immigration Canada. (2021). Découvrir le Canada: les droits et responsabilités liés à la citoyenneté. <https://www.canada.ca/fr/immigration-refugies-citoyennete/organisation/publications-guides/decouvrir-canada.html>

Santos, A. I. (2013). Recursos Educacionais Abertos no Brasil: o estado da arte, desafios e perspectivas para o desenvolvimento e inovação. São Paulo: Comitê Gestor da Internet no Brasil. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000227970>

United States of America. (2015). Resource Guide: Supporting Undocumented Youth. A guide for success in secondary and postsecondary settings. <https://www2.ed.gov/about/overview/focus/supporting-undocumented-youth.pdf>

DETAILED RESULTS:
● AFRICA, ASIA AND
OCEANIA

■ TRADING BLOCS

In terms of trading blocs, those most active on the African continent were selected: the African Union — AU; Asia: Gulf Cooperation Council — GCC and the Commonwealth of Independent States — CIS and one that integrates the Asian and Oceanic continents: Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership — RCEP and Association of Southeast Asian Nations — ASEAN.

| African Union — AU

The African Union is the trading bloc in which we found the most composition (11 items) related to the theme of this report, consisting of treaties, strategic plans and action plans, projects, statutes, handouts, and booklets that articulate the three types of Education and Migration.

I. We start with the “OAU Convention: Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa,” a treaty first published in 1969, at the time of the Organization of African Unity (OAU), and updated in 2019. Signed by the 55 countries of the African Union, it contains the main information on the rights and obligations of refugees in the Union's member countries. The target audience is the authorities of the AU member countries and the refugees themselves. Although this document does not contain data relevant to our topic, it is the basis for a better understanding of the fundamentals of other policies and practices.

II. Another treaty that contains relevant information is the “Kampala Convention,” initially produced in 2009. The 2012 version is currently in force. This convention deals with internally displaced people (IDPs), spelling out the rights and obligations of member countries regarding them. We already have indications of governments' obligation to provide education (p. 18) for this group, showing that education is part of the discussions at the highest level of the Union's multilateral organization.

III. In 2018, the “Protocol to the Treaty Establishing the African Economic Community Relating to Free Movement of Persons, Right of Residence and Right of Establishment” was another treaty that progressively implemented the free movement of persons, right of residence, and establishment on the African continent. He talks about the need to establish a common framework of qualifications to facilitate the movement of people and recognition of curricula (p. 12), representing a parallel with the European Union's open education initiatives.

IV. More recently, we found the “Continental Education Strategy,” a strategic plan that began in 2016 and will continue until 2025. In it, we find the articulation of the three target areas of this report: Open Education, Online Education, and Adult Education in the migrant context, whose objective is to “reorient Africa's

education and training systems to meet the knowledge, competencies, skills, innovation, and creativity needed to nurture African core values and promote sustainable development at national, sub-regional and continental levels” (p. 7). In addition, we find findings linking education and mobility with integration and cooperation in point four: "Harmonized education and training systems are essential for the realization of intra-African mobility and academic integration through regional cooperation" (p. 7); as well as the mention of open/online education to expand tertiary education (p. 19), with a cross-cutting discussion on adult literacy throughout the document.

V. Another interesting initiative is the "Continental Strategy for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) to foster youth employment," a strategy to foster technical and vocational education and training enacted in 2018 and deals with the place of this type of education for the adult public. The main objective of TVET is to "enable the acquisition of knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes in commerce or a professional field, to obtain a decent and justified remuneration" (p. 26), which can be related to the issue of migration in the future.

VI. In this sense, we need to cite "The digital transformation strategy for Africa (2020 — 2030)," which covers the twenties of this century, deals precisely with Open and Online Education, and complements the previous plan. As a strategic plan for the digital and technological development of the African continent, it recommends policies such as: "promoting technology-supported learning, including the creation and expansion of eLearning platforms that offer instant access and use open educational resources" (p. 17) and "promoting policies and strategies that support cooperation in the use of open educational resources (OER) to promote access to educational content" (p. 49).

VII. We finalized the policy survey with "The revised migration policy framework for Africa and plan of action (2018 — 2027)", which covers the nine years indicated in the title, focusing on reviewing migration policies. Here, we find information on Adult Education, such as: "facilitating the integration of all migrants, women, and men, in the labor market, including in the education and training sector, removing gender barriers that restrict the recruitment of women" (p. 16) and findings that place education as the basis for integration and reintegration (p. 38).

VIII. In the production of materials, we raised the "Africa Education Innovations Handbook 2020," which came out recently and touches on all three areas of our theme, serving both the citizens and the leaders of the African Union member countries. The material basically brings together the main initiatives in education, including various open, distance, and/or adult education initiatives.

IX. Another important topic is how higher education works in the field of education. And so, we start with the "Revised Statue of the Pan African University

(PAU)," which in 2016 established the statute of the Pan African University, whose objective is scientific integration between the countries of the continent and internationally competitive scientific development.

X. One development of this initiative is in the area of Online Education, with "Pan African Virtual And E-University (PAVEU)," a project that foresees the development of a digital university under the Pan African University to serve all citizens of AU countries, dealing with topics that touch on Open Education and Adult Education. It aims, therefore, to address the need to accelerate the development of human capital, science, technology, and innovation by increasing access to higher and continuing education in Africa, capitalizing on the digital revolution, and global knowledge. In this sense, we have the "African Virtual University," which works precisely on the basis of virtual and open education.

XII. O último item referente a este bloco político-econômico, não se refere diretamente a União Africana, mas ao continente todo, pois trata-se do sítio eletrônico "OER Initiatives in Africa", que reúne iniciativas em Educação Aberta no continente africano. Nele, é possível encontrar diversas universidades abertas dos países da África, REAs e instituições que tratam do assunto.

| Commonwealth of Independent States — CIS

In the case of the Commonwealth of Independent States, we didn't find any policies or practices that combine the three areas we've covered in this report. So, we looked for materials separately to combine them in this section. In total, there were nine materials, mostly of a legal nature.

I. We begin with the document "Refugees, asylum seekers and displaced persons in the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS)" a 1997 report on the situation of refugees in the CIS by the European Council, a human rights organization founded in 1949.

II. In 2001, "Миграция между странами СНГ: итоги десятилетия (Migration between CIS countries: results of the decade)", was published, a report sponsored by the Open Society in partnership with the United Nations Population Fund and the Management of Social Transformations Programme (MOST), which deals with migration in general. We are talking about data on migration in the CIS space throughout the 1990s, but it does not offer specific information on Open or Online Education.

III. Subsequently, we discovered that in 2009, a United Nations survey entitled "Current Trends in Migration in the Commonwealth of Independent States." This survey, which describes migration more broadly, was commissioned by the UN to examine the trends and social constitution of migratory phenomena in the CIS countries.

IV. We also found documents of a comparative nature, such as “Freedom of Movement and Labour Migration in the Commonwealth of Independent States Comparative Brief on CIS and EU Legislation,” produced by Lilia Ormonbekova. It is a comparative study between the CIS and the EU on freedom of movement and labor migration laws.

V. Of more recent compositions, we find compositions by the CEI itself, such as “Актуальные проблемы миграционной статистики на пространстве СНГ (по материалам Статкомитета СНГ) (Current issues of migration statistics in the CIS (based on materials from the CIS Statistical Committee).” In an article format, it points to the problems surrounding migration data and statistics in the CIS region.

VI. Then, in 2019, we have the publication of “Объемы и направления миграционных потоков в регионе СНГ: возможные методы измерения (Volumes and directions of migration flows in the CIS region: possible measurement methods)” which is a report presenting possible ways of measuring migration flows and trends in the CIS space, based on the issues surrounding data and statistics on this topic.

VII. We also find compositions from outside the CIS, such as those of the University of Wroclaw in Poland, which published “Migration Law of the Commonwealth of Independent States” in 2021. This is a survey carried out by academics on the migration laws of CIS member countries.

VIII. Another composition is located outside the territory of the CIS but focuses on the themes of migration and education. The composition entitled “Educational migration from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States to the Russian Federation” was also produced in 2021 by the following universities: Kazan Federal University in Russia, the University of Science and Education in Vietnam, and Universidad San Ignacio de Loyola in Peru, in which the scholars report on the processes and trends of educational immigration from the CIS countries to Russia.

IX. Finally, the Document KAzAKHstAn/ KyrgyzstAn: Exploitation of migrant workers, protection denied to asylum seekers and refugees, discusses the difficulties of access to education faced by migrants in the two CIS member countries, in particular the denial of education to migrant children and the obstacles to professional integration and higher education.

| Gulf Cooperation Council — GCC

In the Gulf Cooperation Council context, we find practices useful for studies and reflection on Education (Open, Online, and for Adults) and Migration. They are not a direct initiative of the GCC, which shows a certain lack of concern for

migrants. This reinforces the hypothesis that the kafala system prevents greater development of practices and policies for the displaced populations that comprise this trading bloc.

I. First of all, we would like to highlight "The Arab Bureau of Education for the Gulf States," a supra-state organization created in 1975 to support the cooperation and integration of GCC member states in the educational context, which would ideally be a place to search for policies and practices. However, we haven't found any substantial data for this report.

II. In this context, we have the "Arabian Gulf University," a university created in 1979 to serve as a space for integrating adult students from the GCC, who would represent a mobile group in the region. However, only students who are citizens of GCC countries are accepted, and it is also private.

III. Thirdly, we list "Edraak," a platform created by "The Queen Rania Foundation" to serve audiences in the "Arab world," as stated on its website. Generally, it is an open platform with courses in various areas for adults. It also has a program for basic education, with support for students, parents, and teachers, serving the purposes of Open and Distance Education.

IV. As a specific project that also works as Open and Distance Education, we have "Madrasa," started in 2018 by Mohammed Bin Rashid Al Maktoum Global Initiatives. Its target audience is not necessarily adults, but it is an example of the work done in the GCC space. It is an open platform with resources for basic education, including Arabic language lessons.

V. And the last platform we found is "Rwag," created by Fouad Al Farhan and Sami AlHussain, which specifically targets adult Arab students in the field of Open and Distance Education, offers free classes and resources for higher education.

| The Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership — RCEP, Association of Southeast Asian Nations — ASEAN

Regarding these two blocks, we found predominantly reports and some legislation, with some important advances in the last six years, which can be considered elements that can be considered. However, the production does not correspond to the size of this block and the flow of migrants present in it.

I. Let's start with the "ASEAN economic community scorecard" report, published in 2010 by ASEAN. In a single point, it defines some priority areas where services should be shared, including Education (p.5). We found that none of the four proposed modalities refers to Digital or Open Education, usually restricted to recognizing diplomas between countries.

II. In this context, the "ASEAN-Australia-New Zealand Free Trade Area" is worth mentioning. It was created in 2010 to define a free trade area between ASEAN, Australia, and New Zealand. Article 15 (p.99) mentions the recognition of diplomas and indicates that there should be accessible opportunities for the recognition of education, experience, and certificates.

III. A little later, still in 2010, the "2011 ASEAN 5-Year Work Plan on Education (2011-2015)" appeared. This plan provides for implementing an education plan from 2011 to 2015 without mentioning Digital Education but commenting, in its actions, that Information and Communication Technology should "promote education and lifelong learning, particularly in underprivileged communities through open distance education and e-learning" (p.25). There is also a mention of Adult Education as lifelong learning through 5 programs: promoting quality through networks of teachers, principals, administrators, educational institutes, schools, and teacher associations; supporting the development of novice teachers; sharing best practices on teacher incentives, awards, and evaluations; promoting regional teacher accreditation and mobility programs; and increasing regional capacity building efforts for school management, improvement planning, leadership development, and school governance (p.2627). On page 31, we also define the objectives, programs, and activities for Transnational Academic Mobility.

IV. In the report for the following period, "The ASEAN work plan on education 2016 – 2020", we find specific data on Digital Education, i.e., the Priority area 1.3's title is "Advancing the ASEAN Study Program and Higher Education Courses through Online and Cross-border Mobility," integrating Mobility and Distance Education. Further on, in priority area 3.1, we find the title "Expand and improve human and institutional capacity in the development of educational software and online instructional design to improve access to quality education," which points to strengthening the use of ICTs as educational resources. The next priority area, 3.2, is entitled "Strengthen capacity to access and use digital learning through ICT in the ASEAN Member States and provide other training programs to support this," highlighting the formative nature of this educational action plan. We also find policies aimed at Adult Education in priority area 4.1, which aims to "Maximize access to TVET for employment and sustainable development" and supports Technical Vocational Education and Training as part of lifelong learning.

V. Another report that provides information on our subject is "Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025," in which ASEAN defines strategies to create conditions for better integration and connection between member states. The report addresses education at different points: disruptive technology (p.32), digital innovation (p.41) with support for new digital education solutions, the establishment of open databases (p.42), and mobility in higher education linked to the issue of migration (p.89).

VI. In 2019, we Bangkok declaration on advancing partnership in Education for the 2030 agenda for sustainable development in ASEAN, which refers to using technology to structure sustainable education. Thus, in point 2.5, we have the following: "encourage the application of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in teaching and learning, in teacher training, as well as in the management and leadership of education," articulating the use of technology in education in the context of climate change.

VII. We close the survey for this block with the "Roadmap on the ASEAN higher education space 2025," published in 2022, to define the next steps in the field of education for the Member States, defining the ongoing initiative for the "Declaration on the Digital Transformation of Education Systems in ASEAN," which shows a willingness to face changes in education from a technological perspective, but focusing on higher education.

■ COUNTRIES

Regarding countries in Asia, Africa, and Oceania, nine items were found in Turkey, 8 in Australia, 7 in India, 7 in Estonia, 8 in China, 4 in Taiwan, and 2 in Lebanon.

| Australia

Australia represents an important territory through its various government programs, with eight items produced on Adult Education, Distance Education, and Immigrant Education.

I. We start with the "Adult Migrant English Program (AMEP)," promoted by the Australian Government's Department of the Interior. This program aims to obtain basic fluency in English, with the possibility of continuing studies to acquire knowledge of "vocational English." It also offers access to the online platform, which allows for distance learning, and 300 physical teaching posts for migratory groups.

II. Complementary to the course in item I is "AMEPOnline," which allows the study of English without the need to register and with low mobile data usage. It can be accessed anywhere in the world by people who are not yet part of AMEP, serving as an Open Educational Resource (OER) for all those interested, understanding that migrants are often unable to enroll in regular courses.

III. The third online course we found is "Professional learning for adult educators," which integrates the Adult Learning program in Australia with short courses aimed at adult educators and is part of community education, in which we find elements of the three areas targeted in this report. The great contribution of this program is its focus on educators and through distance education. As such, it can be integrated with other programs dedicated to migrants.

IV. Next, we have "Settlement Engagement and Transition Support (SETS)," also promoted by the Australian government. The program supports immigrants in different areas, such as education, employability, transport, housing, and health, since the aim is to help immigrants settle in and get involved with the host community. Immigrants in this program can later be referred to educational programs such as the "Adult Migrant English Program (AMEP)" and "The Skills for Education and Employment (SEE)," which offer skills in education with employability in mind. Another important aspect is that the program strengthens the community and the individual, known as the customer.

V. Linked to this government support, we also find "The national settlement framework," guidelines in document format that contain information about immigrant support programs in Australia. One of the priority areas is Education

and Training. The target audience is permanent and long-term temporary migrants at all three educational levels (nursery, youth, and adult).

VI. Given the current and intense migratory flows around the world, the government has also prepared the "Humanitarian Settlement Program (HSP)," which is aimed at so-called "humanitarian" migrants for their first five years in Australia. The program has regional branches, helping employers who want to employ migrants, working with the idea of raising awareness, and offering psychological assistance.

VII. The last of the government programs aimed at accommodating and integrating immigrants is the "National Settlement Outcomes Standards," which has been responsible for the quality of care in this area since 2015. One of the priority areas is Education and Training, with nine points that bring together best practices:

A. Education and training providers have strategies for involving newly graduated individuals and newcomer communities. They offer flexible learning options, such as part-time, face-to-face and/or online study.

B. Education and training programs that provide integrated and intensive English as a support to facilitate learning and improve everyday life in Australia.

C. Teaching English helps people to be ready for the job market.

D. The education and training programs recognize pre-arrival skills and facilitate additional training whenever necessary.

E. The education and training programs offer many opportunities for work, experience, and on-the-job training.

F. Women are supported to access education and training programs, through available and affordable childcare and by promoting the value of women's education to different cultures.

G. Young people, their families, or guardians receive targeted support to understand and navigate the education and training options available to them and can build relationships with education and training providers;

H. Schools and teachers are aware of and receptive to the educational challenges faced by young newcomers, which are distinct from those faced by Australian-born and non-migrant peers.

I. Newcomers are supported to overcome practical barriers to participation, such as increasing digital literacy and security and enabling access to appropriate IT equipment.

VIII. Finally, we mention the network of open universities, "Open Universities Australia," which has existed since 1993 and encompasses 28 Australian higher education institutions. Based on the concept of Distance Education, it offers free courses, most of them without prerequisites, at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels.

| China

In this country, we found a variety of compositions, including legislation, reports, government agencies, and courses, for a total of six items.

I. We'll start with the "National Immigration Administration — NIA," a government agency created in 2018. It is part of the Ministry of Public Security and deals with issues relating to migrants' presence on national territory. On the website, you can find laws and regulations, policy interpretations, news, and statistics, as well as guidance for foreigners and by the national office.

II. As far as legislation is concerned, we will start with the "Exit and Entry Administration Law of the People's Republic of China," a law enacted in 2012, in which the conditions for entry and exit into the country are described, with Article 42 being of particular interest: "The competent education department of the State Council shall, in conjunction with the relevant departments of the State Council, establish an administrative system for foreign students working to support their studies in China and set regulations on the scope of jobs and the limit of working time for such foreign students," assigning responsibility to the state for balancing work and study activities.

III. The following year, in 2013, the "Regulations of the People's Republic of China on Administration of the Entry and Exit of Foreigners," normative instructions on the entry and exit of foreigners in Chinese territory, discussing the rights and responsibilities (including in the educational context) of temporary or long-term residents, which we can frame as a way of dealing with migrants.

IV. For 2019, the "Comprehensive Statistics on Entry-Exit Frontier Inspection (Q2, 2019)," a report that provides a comprehensive statistical picture of foreigners entering and leaving China, which can be used to understand the migration situation in the country.

V. The NIA produces materials to help immigrants stay and integrate in the country, such as the Reception Guides for 2020 and 2022, containing information on formal and non-formal education (p.36). The "Morando na China (Living in China)" Guide provides a wealth of information for foreigners/immigrants. It offers the "Online Chinese Course" with videos and audios that teach different linguistic and cultural aspects of the country.

VI. Closing the survey of this country, we include the "XuetangX," a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) produced in 2013 by Tsinghua University, designed for research, interaction, and confirmation of the best practices of the "MOE Research Center for Online Education." In addition, as one of China's first innovation programs and entrepreneurship demonstration bases, XuetangX is

maintained by the vice secretary general of the Chinese Higher Education Association and is an online education platform for UNESCO's Innovation Cluster for Entrepreneurship Education (ICEE).

| Taiwan

Despite the lack of consensus on the status of this territory or country, we have decided to present four Taiwanese compositions separately, as they are OERs or MOOCs created by higher education institutions in the area of Education interfacing with Industry and Entrepreneurship.

I. First, we present "Smelearning," an electronic site created by the Taiwanese Ministry of Finance's Administration of Small and Medium Enterprises in the context of the "Online Education for Small and Medium Enterprises" program. Classified as a lifelong learning program, it presents six learning dimensions related to entrepreneurship and highlights the importance of technology.

II. Secondly, we have "IUCTII," the result of a program to promote young industrialists, carried out by the Industrial Technology Research Institute and Office for Industrial Development with the support of higher education institutions and companies. It defines three types of programs: "inworking," for individuals who are already employed; "self-learning," for those who are self-taught; and a more comprehensive platform for developing cooperation between companies and universities. This proposal seemed interesting to us as a possibility of welcoming people on the move (forced or voluntary) so that they could have the opportunity to continue their training through continuing education.

III. In the text "Developing an OER Website and Analyzing Its Use during the COVID-19 Pandemic," we find information about the production of an OER aimed at teaching English in the country, with the website called "Cool English," supported and financed by the Ministry of Education, aimed at producing resources in rural areas, but which was partially redirected to meet the demands arising from the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (an important link for thinking about Migration, Education, and Health).

IV. Another Internet initiative is that of National Taipei University, which has a "Resources" tab on its International Relations Office page. Here, we can find mentions of "Digital Learning Resources" and "Distance Learning." These Two Terms show how the higher education institutions (HEI) have been concerned with this issue. The Digital Learning Resources section contains:

A. "NTU Speech," an archive and live streaming platform for lectures held at NTU. It has more than 2,500 speeches, including speeches by Nobel Prize winners.

B. "NTU OpenCourseWare (NTU OCW)" is a platform created by the institution for online courses and lectures, with more than 200 courses available. As a university that considers open access to education important, NTU is a member of the "Open Education Consortium."

C. "NTU MOOC x Coursera," a partnership established with the online learning platform Coursera, currently offers more than 50 courses, with more than 24,000 students and 4,000 certificates of completion. On the other hand, Distance Learning has a website, "OpenCourseWare," on which previous teaching and learning experiences are stored.

| India

The seven items surveyed for this country consist of government documents and programs produced by the Ministry of Education and explicitly aimed at Open and Distance Education, including for adult audiences. However, they do not further indicate their use in a migratory context. This seems feasible because these proposals aim to serve more vulnerable groups and/or those without access to formal face-to-face education.

I. We started with "SWAYAM," a government program produced and executed by the Ministry of Education. Its purpose is to offer free distance learning courses from Basic Education to higher education. More specifically, the program was designed to achieve the three fundamental principles of the Indian Education Policy: accessibility, equity, and quality. This effort aims to provide better-quality teaching and learning resources to the population, including the most deprived. The aim is to reduce digital inequality among students who, according to the text of the program: "have not been untouched by the digital revolution and have not been able to enter the mainstream of the economy of knowledge". It also has nine national coordinators who deal with specific aspects of different types of education, grouped into four areas: School Education, Out-of-School Education, Undergraduate Education, and Postgraduate Education.

II. As an offshoot of this first program and its four areas, the "National Institute of Open Schooling (NIOS)," was created in School Education. This institute provides not only open courses in Basic Education but also teacher training courses to serve the public.

III. A second product of "SWAYAM," developed in the area of Out-of-School Education, is the "Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU)." This open university offers various courses free of charge and is closer to the demands of people on the move by providing for study outside the classroom as a strategy for including people in the school system.

IV. Regarding documents, we can mention the "Guideline for Developing Online Courses for SWAYAM", a 2017 guideline with parameters for creating online courses in the context of the government program presented above.

V. A more specific document is the "University Grants Commission Gazette: Credit Framework for Online Learning Courses through SWAYAM", through which it is possible to define the guidelines for awarding credits for online courses, as well as the production of MOOCs and hybrid teaching modes, following SWAYAM's four-quadrant approach: e-tutorial, e-content, discussion and evaluation.

VI. "All India Council for Technical Education Gazette: Credit Framework for Online Learning Courses through SWAYAM," which are guidelines developed to guide the creation of online courses for technical education.

VII. One program produced in a supranational context in which India participates is the "Commonwealth Educational Media Centre for Asia (CEMCA)." This entity, started in 1994 by the Commonwealth of Learning (COL) and based in Canada, brings together Asian countries willing to think about learning collectively. It aims to develop distance education and the use of technology in educational courses.

| Lebanon

As already mentioned, this country is known for having a notable emigrant community, including Brazilians, and currently represents one of the countries in the Middle East that receives the most refugees and immigrants from the same region. Given this specific reality, we looked for best practices and policies and found two platforms that support refugee students, focusing mainly on young people.

I. The first localized platform organization is "Kiron," started in 2015 by a non-governmental organization to assist the growing number of localized platform organizations. "Kiron" began in 2015 by a non-governmental organization to help the ever-increasing number of Syrian refugees operating in Lebanon, Germany, and Jordan. Because it operates in different territories, including the country on the European continent that has received the most refugees, it produced this MOOC, or Massive Open Educational Resource, for this specific group. In Lebanon, it operates in a hybrid way with face-to-face and distance learning classes, serving both young and adult audiences.

II. The second production, "Tabshoura," is a platform created by the Lebanese Alternative Learning (LAL) organization to promote alternative learning methods. It is free to access and based on the Lebanese curriculum. It combines educational content in MOOCs for Lebanese students in English, French, and Arabic. We noticed that it has mechanisms that can be accessed offline, which could be an interesting strategy for migrants and refugees who often don't have permanent access to the internet.

| Turkey

This country, located between Europe and Asia and receiving an abundance of people on the move, has nine items in institutions, such as documents, resources, and academic productions, that help us understand what is produced in this territory.

I. We started with the Turkish Council, an institution founded by educators in 1985 to offer educational services to international students. They help with visa and residence permit applications and offer career support, accommodation search services, and health insurance. It is a Non-Governmental Organization inspired by the work of the British Council to meet the country's high immigration demand since the 1980s.

II. We continue with "Sustainable approaches to humanitarian assistance in the field of language education for adult refugees in Turkey," a report produced in 2019 by the Istanbul Policy Center — Mercator Policy Brief, aimed at recommending ways to improve the sustainability of humanitarian assistance provided by civil society organizations and state institutions to support language education for refugees. This is done by offering information on the state of existing language teaching options for refugees in Turkey, highlighting the potential risks and limitations, and then recommending maintaining humanitarian funds for language teaching.

III. In third place is "Designing Culturally Sensitive Massive Open Online Courses: Learning Culture and MOOCs in Turkey," a teaching material created in 2018 by Cengiz Hakan Aydin and Buket Kip Kayabaş from Anadolu University in Eskişehir. The aim of this manuscript is threefold: first, it is a summary of the development of the philosophy of openness in higher education globally; then, based on the available literature, it draws a picture of the effects of culture on open and distance learning; and, further on, the manuscript provides an insight into the general cultural characteristics of Turkish society and the learning culture shaped by past and present implementations; finally, it lists a series of recommendations for those designing MOOCs for the Turkish audience.

IV. In addition to the production of best practices and policies in Turkey, we have found several academic texts that report on the situation in the country and, for this reason, we cite here the "Comparing the Migrants Education Policies of Turkey and Germany," a 2020 academic article written by Faik Tanrıku of Istanbul Medipol University for the International Conferences on Social Science. The article examines the differences in migrant education policies in Turkey and Germany, which can serve as a basis for future comparative studies that will study what is produced in each country/block.

V. Another interesting academic text is "The international migration and foreign

policy nexus: the case of Syrian refugee crisis and Turkey", produced in 2018 by N. Ela Gökalp Aras and Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, from the Department of International Relations at Gediz University. Here, we demonstrate the importance and impact of foreign policy orientations on immigration and asylum policies. We discuss how “foreign” policy and “asylum” policy are intertwined and generate differences in coping with the mass influx, focusing on the Syrian refugee crisis and Turkey’s policy responses.

VI. Hasan Aydın Yildiz of the Technical University's 2012 publication, “Multicultural Education Curriculum Development in Turkey,” provides multicultural educators with an overview of research into multicultural education curriculum development. In addition, this article offers selected ideas from successful multicultural programs in the United States and elsewhere and discusses whether these ideas could be useful in the Turkish system.

VII. In the chapter “WarInduced Immigration and Education: Syrian Refugees' Education in Turkey,” published in 2019 by Binali Tunç and Çiğdem Zeynep Can, it is possible to find information on the educational status of Syrian refugees in Turkey, with indications of potential actions that can better serve this public, especially if we think of groups in displacement caused by war conflicts.

VIII. Another 2016 text dealing with the presence of Syrian refugees is “The Educational Opportunities and Challenges of Syrian Refugee Students in Turkey: Temporary Education Centers and Beyond” by Aras Bülent and Yasun Salih of the Istanbul Policy Center. It assesses the educational opportunities and challenges for Syrian refugees in Turkey. It analyzes the role of Temporary Education Centers (TEC) in integrating Syrian students into the Turkish education system, an experience that could be contemplated for other realities and contexts.

IX. Finally, Seyda Subasi from the Institute of Educational Sciences at the University of Vienna in Austria wrote “Adult Education Efforts for Refugees: A Case of a Border City in Turkey” in 2018. This article focuses on adult education efforts for refugee adults in a Turkish border town. It is important because it focuses on a population no longer old enough to receive basic education.

| Estonia

This country does not officially belong to the region covered by this report. Still, we have chosen to include it now because it is, in a way, in a transitional space since it is part of the European Union and in the past was part of the Soviet Union, containing a reasonable number of CIS citizens, which may allow the reader to consider the reasons for the lack of other initiatives on the themes proposed by this report in the different countries that once made up the CIS. This

condition resulted in a survey of seven items, including programs, documents, and academic production.

I. The first composition found was "Integration Policy Instruments in Estonia," a reception program created by the Estonian Ministry of the Interior to develop comprehensive, flexible, and adequate support services for newly arrived immigrants to facilitate their adaptation. It involves five types of policy, including Education Policy, and five modules covering topics such as society, state, culture, rights, the European Union, family, work, entrepreneurship, study, research, and children/young people.

II. In addition to this reception program, there is an adaptation program called "Settle in Estonia," drawn up by the Estonian Ministry of Culture. It consists of several training programs and provides an overview of how the Estonian state and society function and how everyday life is organized.

III. Also in this context, "Integration policy instruments in Estonia," which is part of the project "INTERACT - Researching Third Country Nationals' Integration as a Three-way Process Immigrants, Countries of Emigration and Countries of Immigration as Actors of Integration" and aims to integrate both immigrants and countries of emigration and immigration. Regarding education, different proposals and activities are put forward to support the goals of integration, such as: "language classes, counseling, language immersion, integrated study programs, and civic education" (p.12). In addition, it mentions institutions responsible for implementing these instruments, such as "The Integration and Migration Foundation Our People (MISA)," which aims to: "instigate and support activities designed to achieve the integration of Estonian society between Estonians and non-Estonians; instigate and support activities associated with migration and immigration; and to support the adaptation of non-Estonians to the Estonian cultural space and their inclusion in active social communities."

IV. Looking back at the country's past, it is important to look at its insertion into the Soviet Union, the effects of which are still being felt. Examples of how the government works with the presence of Russians, a population that is no longer considered national/local, can be found in "Attempts at Intercultural and Multicultural Education in Estonia," published in 1997 by Edgar Krull of the International Association for Citizenship, Social and Economic Education. This article deals with the problems of multiculturalism created by Russian immigration to Estonia during the Soviet annexation, outlining some of the foundations of intercultural and multicultural education for migrants that can be related to the experience of the CIS.

V. Thinking ahead, we find the article "Refugee Quota: Is Estonia Ready to Receive Refugees? A Review of the Literature on Migration and Ethnic Minorities in Estonia," which is a survey prepared by Aminul Islam from the European

Integration Studies Journal. It analyzes the literature on migration and ethnic minorities in Estonia.

VI. Another way of thinking about Estonia is compared to other countries worldwide, as was done in "Comparative Cartography of Adult Education for Migrants in Cyprus, Estonia, Malta, and Scotland," a text produced in 2021 by Maria Brown, Maria N. Gravani, Bonnie Slade, and Larissa Jõgi in the book *Learner-Centered Education for Adult Migrants in Europe*. This chapter discusses and critically examines legislative and policy practices in Cyprus, Scotland, Malta, and Estonia regarding providing education for adult migrants.

VII. An account of the practices developed from the same book, which is important for this survey, is "Learner-Centred Education and Adult Education for Migrants in Estonia" by Larissa Jõgi and Katrin Karu. This is a case study that analyzes the implementation of the "Curso de formação de línguas" (Language training course) module, part of the Adaptação Acolhedora Program mentioned in section II.

■ REFERENCES

Abazov, R. (2009). "Current Trends in Migration in the Commonwealth of Independent States". Nova York: UNDP. <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/19220/>

Adult Learning Australia (2023). Professional learning for adult educators. <https://communityeducation.net.au/>

Adult Migrant English Program - AMEP (2023). <https://immi.homeaffairs.gov.au/settling-in-australia/amep/about-the-program>

Adult Migrant English Program – AMEP ONLINE (2023). <https://ameponline.homeaffairs.gov.au/>

African Union (1974). Oau Convention: Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa. Addis Ababa: African Union Headquarters. https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/36400-treaty-36400-treaty-oau_convention_1963.pdf

African Union (2012). African Union Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons in Africa (Kampala Convention). Addis Ababa: African Union Headquarters. https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/36846-treaty-kampala_convention.pdf

African Union (2016). Continental Education Strategy for Africa CESA 2016 – 2025. Addis Ababa: African Union Headquarters. <https://ecosoc.africa.int/sites/default/files/files/2021-09/continental-strategy-education-africa-english.pdf>

African Union (2016). Revised Statute of the Pan-African University (PAU). Addis Ababa: African Union Headquarters. https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/33127-treaty-0059_-_revised_statute_pan_african_university_e.pdf

African Union (2018). Continental Strategy for Technical and Vocational Educational and Training (TVET) to Foster Youth Employment. Addis Ababa: African Union Headquarters. https://au.int/sites/default/files/pressreleases/35308-pr-tvet-english_-_final_2.pdf

African Union (2018). The Migration Policy Framework for Africa (MPFA). Addis Ababa: African Union Headquarters. <https://au.int/en/documents/20181206/migration-policy-framework-africa-mpfa>

African Union (2018). Protocol to the Treaty Establishing the African Economic Community Relating to Free Movement of Persons, Right of Residence and Right

of Establishment. Addis Ababa: African Union Headquarters.
[https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/36403-treaty-protocol on free movement of persons in africa e.pdf](https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/36403-treaty-protocol%20on%20free%20movement%20of%20persons%20in%20africa%20e.pdf)

African Union (2020). Africa Education Innovations Handbook 2020. Addis Ababa: African Union Commission. [https://au.int/sites/default/files/documents/41358-doc-Africa Education Innovations Handbook 2020 EN.pdf](https://au.int/sites/default/files/documents/41358-doc-Africa%20Education%20Innovations%20Handbook%202020%20EN.pdf)

African Union (2020). The Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa (2020-2030). Addis Ababa: African Union Headquarters. [https://openresearch-repository.anu.edu.au/bitstream/1885/278587/1/GhaEcon 24.pdf](https://openresearch-repository.anu.edu.au/bitstream/1885/278587/1/GhaEcon%2024.pdf)

African Union Commission (2016). Human Development Education Science, Technology and Innovation Youth - Report of Annual Continental Activities 2016 – RACA. Addis Ababa: African Union Commission. <https://archives.au.int/bitstream/handle/123456789/9785/2016%20RACA.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

African Union Development Agency (2023). Pan African Virtual and E-University (PAVEU). <https://www.nepad.org/agenda-2063/flagship-project/pan-african-virtual-and-e-university-paveu#:~:text=This%20project%20aims%20to%20address,digital%20revolution%20and%20global%20knowledge.>

The Arab Bureau of Education for the Gulf States (2023). <https://en.abegs.org/home>

Arabian Gulf University (2023). <https://www.agu.edu.bh/en>

Aras, E. G. & Mencütek, Z. Ş. (2015). "The international migration and foreign policy nexus: the case of Syrian refugee crisis and Turkey," Migration Letters, Transnational Press London, UK, vol. 12(3), pages 193-208, September. <https://migrationletters.com/index.php/ml/article/view/274>

Aras, Bülent & Yasun, Salih (2016) The educational opportunities and challenges of Syrian refugee students in Turkey: temporary education centers and beyond. Monograph. Istanbul Policy Center. <http://ipc.sabanciuniv.edu/en/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/Bulent-Aras-and-Salih-Yasun-11.pdf>

ASEAN (2010). Economic Community Scorecard: Charting Progress Towards Regional Economic Integration. Jakarta: ASEAN Secretariat. <https://www.asean.org/wp-content/uploads/images/archive/publications/AEC%20Scorecard.pdf>

ASEAN-Australia-New Zealand FTA (2010). <https://www.dfat.gov.au/trade/agreements/in-force/aanzfta/asean-australia-new-zealand-free-trade-agreement>

ASEAN (2012). Year Work Plan on Education (2011-2015). Jakarta: ASEAN Secretariat. <https://cil.nus.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/2011-2015-ASEAN-5-Year-Education-WP.pdf>

ASEAN (2016). The Asean Work Plan On Education 2016 – 2020. <https://cil.nus.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/2016-2020-Education-WP.pdf>

ASEAN (2017). Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025. Jakarta, ASEAN Secretariat. <https://asean.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/47.-December-2017-MPAC2025-2nd-Reprint-.pdf>

ASEAN (2019). Bangkok Declaration on Advancing Partnership in Education for 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development in ASEAN. <https://cil.nus.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/2019-Bangkok-Declrtn-Advancing-Partnership-Education-2030-Agenda.pdf>

ASEAN (2022). Roadmap on the Asean Higher Education Space 2025 And Its Implamation Plan. https://asean.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/ASEAN-Higher-Education-Space-2025_rev-1.pdf

Australian Government. Department of Home Affairs (s.d.). The National Settlement Framework. <https://immi.homeaffairs.gov.au/settlement-services-subsite/files/the-national-settlement-framework.pdf>

Australian Government. Department of Home Affairs (2020). Humanitarian Settlement Program (HSP). <https://immi.homeaffairs.gov.au/settling-in-australia/humanitarian-settlement-program/about-the-program/humanitarian-settlement-regional-australia>

Australian Government. Department of Home Affairs (2023). Immigration and citizenship. <https://immi.homeaffairs.gov.au/>

Australian Government. Department of Employment and Workplace Relations. (2023). The Skills for Education and Employment program. [https://www.dewr.gov.au/skills-education-and-employment#:~:text=The%20Skills%20for%20Education%20and%20Employment%20\(SEE%20Program%20provides%20training,right%20through%20to%20remote%20communities.](https://www.dewr.gov.au/skills-education-and-employment#:~:text=The%20Skills%20for%20Education%20and%20Employment%20(SEE%20Program%20provides%20training,right%20through%20to%20remote%20communities.)

Aydin, C. H. & Kayabaş, B. K. (2018). Designing Culturally Sensitive Massive Open Online Courses: Learning Culture and MOOCs in Turkey. In E. Toprak & E. Kumtepe (Eds.), Supporting Multiculturalism in Open and Distance Learning Spaces (pp. 208-221). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-3076-3.ch011>

Aydin, H. (2012). Multicultural Education Curriculum Development in Turkey. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(3), 277. <https://www.richtmann.org/journal/index.php/mjss/article/view/11087>

Beliakova, K.(2020).Migration Law of the Commonwealth of Independent States. *Wroclaw Review of Law, Administration & Economics*,10(1) 72-92. <https://doi.org/10.2478/wrlae-2020-0006>

Brown, M., Gravani, M. N., Slade, B., & Jögi, L. (2021). "Chapter 3 Comparative Cartography of Adult Education for Migrants in Cyprus, Estonia, Malta and Scotland". In *Learner-Centred Education for Adult Migrants in Europe*. Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004461529_003

Chen H. (2020). Developing an OER Website and Analyzing Its Use during the COVID-19 Pandemic *English Teaching & Learning*. 2020 Jan;44(4):451-461.

Commonwealth Educational Media Centre for Asia – CEMCA(2023). <https://www.cemca.org/>

Council of Europe (1997). Refugees, asylum-seekers and displaced persons in the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS). Estrasburg: Committee on Migration, Refugees and Demography. <https://assembly.coe.int/nw/xml/XRef/X2H-Xref-ViewHTML.asp?FileID=7747&lang=EN>

Edraak (2023). <https://www.edraak.org/en/>

Estonian Ministry of Interior. (s.d.). Welcoming programme. <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/525062015003/consolide>

European University Institute (2019) *Interact*. Firenze: Migration Policy Centre. <http://interact-project.eu/>

FIDH - International Federation for Human Rights (2009). Kazakhstan/ Kyrgyzstan: Exploitation of migrant workers, protection denied to asylumseekers and refugees. Paris: FIDH. https://www2.ohchr.org/english/bodies/cerd/docs/ngos/FIDH_Kazakhstan_76.pdf

Industrial Technology Research Institute (2023). Professional Learning Programs. <https://www.itri.org.tw/english/>

Islam, A. (2016). Refugee Quota: Is Estonia Ready to Receive Refugees? A Review of the Literature on Migration and Ethnic Minorities in Estonia. *European Integration Studies*, No. 10, pp. 73–80. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5755/j01.eis.0.10.16104>

Jõgi, L., & Karu, K. (2021). "Chapter 4 Learner-Centred Education and Adult Education for Migrants in Estonia". In Learner-Centred Education for Adult Migrants in Europe. Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill.

https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004461529_004

Kajumovna Karimova, L., Ravil'evna Sagitova, V., Andreevna Kirpichnikova, A., y Van Hoang, H. (2021). Educational migration from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States to the Russian Federation. *Propósitos y Representaciones*, 9(SPE2), e1007.

<https://doi.org/10.20511/pyr2021.v9nSPE2.1007>

Kiron (2023). Kiron Lebanon. <https://www.kiron.ngo/about>

Krull, E. (1997). Attempts at Intercultural and Multicultural Education in Estonia. *Citizenship, Social and Economics Education*, 2(1), 33-46.

<https://doi.org/10.2304/csee.1997.2.1.33>

Mohammed bin Rashid al Maktum Global Initiatives (2023). Madrasa.

<https://madrasa.org/>

Ministry of Education (2019). Cool English. <https://www.coolenglish.edu.tw/>

National Immigration Administration – NIA (2012) Exit and Entry Administration Law of the People's Republic of China. <https://en.nia.gov.cn/n147418/n147458/c155978/content.html>

National Immigration Administration – NIA (2013). Regulations of the People's Republic of China on Administration of the Entry and Exit of Foreigners. http://en.moj.gov.cn/pdf_RegulationsofthePeople%27sRepublicofChinaonAdministrationoftheEntryandExitofForeigners.pdf

National Immigration Administration – NIA (2019). Comprehensive Statistics on Entry-Exit Frontier Inspection (Q1, 2019). <https://en.nia.gov.cn/n147418/n147473/index.html>

National Immigration Administration – NIA (2020). A Welcome Guide to China. <https://en.nia.gov.cn/English/magazine/WelcometoChina/mobile/index.html#p=1>

National Immigration Administration – NIA (2022). Living in China. <https://en.nia.gov.cn/English/magazine/living/mobile/index.html#p=5>

National Immigration Administration – NIA (2022). A Welcome Guide to China. <https://www.nia.gov.cn/2022en/mobile/index.html>

National Immigration Administration – NIA (2023). <https://en.nia.gov.cn/index.html>

National Immigration Administration – NIA (2023). Online Chinese Teaching. <https://en.nia.gov.cn/n147428/n147503/index.html>

National Taiwan University (2023) Office of International Affairs. <https://oia.ntu.edu.tw/en/internationalstudents/allyouneedtoknow/campuslife/resources>

National Taiwan University (2019). NTU Speech. <https://www.dlc.ntu.edu.tw/en/ntu-speech-2/>

National Taiwan University (2023). Coursera. National Taiwan University. <https://www.coursera.org/taiwan>

National Taiwan University (2023). OpenCourseWare. <http://ocw.aca.ntu.edu.tw/ntu-ocw/>

Nimer, M. & Oruç, T. (2019). Sustainable Approaches to Humanitarian Assistance in the Field of Language Education for Adult Refugees in Turkey. Istanbul: Istanbul Policy Center. <https://ipc.sabanciuniv.edu/Content/Images/CKeditorImages/20200313-11034972.pdf>

OER Africa (2023). OER Initiatives in Africa. <https://www.oerafrica.org/oer-initiatives-africa>

Open Universities Australia (2023). <https://www.open.edu.au/>

Ormonbekova, L. (s.d.). Freedom of Movement and Labour Migration in the Commonwealth of Independent States Comparative Brief on CIS and EU Legislation. https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/146223/Ormonbekova_2.eng.pdf

Republic of Estonia. Ministry of Culture. (2023) Adaptation Programme. <https://www.kul.ee/en/cultural-diversity-and-integration/adaptation/adaptation-programme>

Rwaq (2023). <https://www.rwaq.org/>

Settlement Council of Australia (2020). National Settlement Outcomes Standards. <https://scoa.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/NSOS-2020.pdf>

Smelearning (2023). <https://www.smelearning.org.tw/>

Subasi, S. (2018). Adult education efforts for refugees: a case of a border city in Turkey. *Dyskursy Młodych Andragogów*, (19), 79–93. <https://bibliotekanauki.pl/articles/431566>

SWAYAM (2016). All India Council for Technical Education Gazette: Credit Framework for Online Learning Courses through SWAYAM.
https://storage.googleapis.com/swayam2_central/swayam1/wqimgtest_9da02ba8-bdd8-409c-afdb-645e6dbc544f.pdf

SWAYAM (2017). Guidelines for developing Online Courses for SWAYAM.
https://storage.googleapis.com/swayam2_central/swayam1/wqimgtest_f8b95943-b963-49b9-85ed-416f2e15d1b4.pdf

SWAYAM (2023). <https://swayam.gov.in/about>

SWAYAM (2023). National Institute of Open Schooling (NIOS).
https://swayam.gov.in/nc_details/NIOS.

SWAYAM (2023). Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU).
https://swayam.gov.in/nc_details/IGNOU

Tabshoura (2023). <https://tabshoura.com/>

Tanrikulu, F. (2020). Comparing of Migrants Education Policies of Turkey and Germany. ICONSR 2020 - International Conference on Social Science Research. Budva, Montenegro: Association of Kutbilge Academicians, Isparta, Turkey.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347911347_Comparing_of_Migrants_Education_Policies_of_Turkey_and_Germany

Tunç, B. & Can, Ç. Z. (2019). War-Induced Immigration and Education: Syrian Refugees' Education in Turkey. In I. Management Association (Ed.), Immigration and the Current Social, Political, and Economic Climate: Breakthroughs in Research and Practice (pp. 327-352). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-6918-3.ch018>

Turkish Council (2023). Turkey's International Culture and Education Institution.
<https://www.turkishcouncil.org/>

United Nations Economic Commission for Europe – UNECE (2019). Объемы и направления миграционных [Volumes e direções de migração fluxos na região da CEI: possíveis métodos de medição]. Geneva: UNECE. https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2022-04/1%20Admin%20CISSTAT_v2.pdf

XuetangX (2023). <https://www.xuetangx.com/>

Демоскоп Weekly (2001). Миграция между странами СНГ: итоги десятилетия [Migração entre os países da CEI: resultados da década]. Moscou: Demoscope https://www.demoscope.ru/weekly/knigi/ns_r01/razdel5q5_10.html

Статистика международной миграции. Практическое руководство для стран Восточной Европы и Центральной Азии. [Estatísticas de migração internacional. Guia prático para países da Europa Oriental e Ásia Central]. ЕЭК ООН, ЮНФПА, 2011. <https://e-cis.info/cooperation/3049/78437/>

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